

**Sterol Biosynthesis as an
Antimicrobial Target in
Acanthamoeba species**

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Abstract

The species of the genus *Acanthamoeba* are normally free-living protozoan parasites, found ubiquitously in the environment. However, they are also opportunistic pathogens capable of causing severe diseases. The most common of these is *Acanthamoeba* keratitis (AK) a severe infection of the cornea that may result in blindness. Many of the drugs used to treat *Acanthamoeba* infections have a poor effect and are arduous on the patient, additionally while AK is treated with combination therapy, these combinations are rarely confirmed for effect or examined *in-vitro*. To this end, the studies herein demonstrate the effectiveness of squalene epoxidase inhibitors as a potential new treatment option. Located on the membrane, squalene epoxidase catalyses the first step in sterol synthesis. While never before used as a drug target in *Acanthamoeba* spp. previous attempts to utilise antifungals in *Acanthamoeba* spp treatment has had success. To this end, five antifungal squalene epoxidase inhibitors were tested against test strains of *Acanthamoeba* spp. The results showed that terbinafine restricts amoeba growth at 4 μ M at 96 hours. A range of statins was also investigated, with pitavastatin, showing amoebicidal capabilities at 2.29 μ M. However, despite our hypothesis that the inhibitors would have a synergistic effect, no interaction was detected when the compounds were used together. Two biocides chlorhexidine (CHX) and Polyhexamethylene biguanide (PHMB) were also investigated with the primary factor of looking at their synergistic potential. While CHX showed low to no synergy with any of the compounds tested PHMB showed synergy with nearly all compounds used and showed particular synergy with Terbinafine. To further elucidate on the function of these compounds, GC-MS was utilised. Two previously used methods were compared during the optimisation process, and a new optimised method was created exclusively for *Acanthamoeba* spp. The results gained clearly show that terbinafine acts through squalene inhibition while voriconazole, a previously used sterol inhibitor functions through the inhibition of obtifoliol. Attempts were also made to create a GFP-expressing *Acanthamoeba* spp cell line. A GFP-expressing plasmid was successfully created, and a transfection process was optimised

for the amoeba. However microscopic analysis showed that *Acanthamoeba* spp are autofluorescence and rendered the GFP less active. The plasmid was switched to an RFP. This plasmid was created and confirmed via sequencing.

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List of Abbreviations

AK	Acanthamoeba keratitis
BBB	Blood brain barrier
BSTFA	(N,O-Bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide)
CA	Cutaneous Acanthamoebiasis
cDNA	complementary deoxyribonucleic acid
CHX	Chlorhexidine
CNS	central nervous system
DMSO	Dimethyl sulphoxide
DNA	deoxyribonucleic acid
GAE	granulomatous amoebic encephalitis
GC-MS	Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry
HIV	human immunodeficiency virus
MBP	mannose binding protein
PCR	polymerase chain reaction
PG	Peptone and Glucose
PHMB	Polyhexamethylene biguanide

SAP	Shrimp Alkaline Phosphatase
SE	standard error
Spp	Species
TENs	10mM Tris-HCl (Sigma,UK), 1mM EDTA (Sigma,UK), 150mM NaCl (Sigma,UK) and 0.5% SDS (Sigma,UK)

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Chapter 1 Literature Review

1.1 Background

Acanthamoeba is a genus of the phylum Amoebozoa, single-celled protists, and bacterivorous found ubiquitously in the environment, acting as secondary fermenters. Free-living, their environment necessitates adaptability easily demonstrated by their diverse living conditions. *Acanthamoeba* are found in nearly all environments, including air, fresh water, seawater, sewage and tap water(Lass *et al.*, 2017; Basher *et al.*, 2018). Water treatment to reduce microbial load is also ineffective against *Acanthamoeba*, with this protist being detected in both bottled water and chlorinated swimming pools(Canals *et al.*, 2015; Gabriel and Panaligan, 2020).

The severity of disease caused by *Acanthamoeba* is reliant on the individual's immunocompetence and the site of infection. Under these conditions, there are three potential disease outcomes; Granulomatous Amoebic Encephalitis (GAE), a near always fatal disease of the central nervous system (CNS), Cutaneous Acanthamoebiasis (CA) infection of the skin and sinus and *Acanthamoeba* keratitis (AK) a severe, and emerging disease of the eye. GAE and CA rarely occur outside of immunocompromised individuals, with AK's rise in the immunocompetent linked directly to contact lens use.

Due to the nature of *Acanthamoeba* spp. infections are generally isolated although severe. The disease outcome is binary; should treatment prove successful then the pathogenic *Acanthamoeba* spp. are eliminated, alternatively surgical intervention is required resulting in enucleation. Currently the only known mechanism of *Acanthamoeba* spp. continuing infection beyond the initial host is through exceedingly rare transplants were the organ was previously contaminated with *Acanthamoeba* spp. (Salameh *et al.*, 2015a).

1.2 Discovery

Amoebae are single-celled organisms that manipulate their membrane to produce tentacular protuberances, termed pseudopodia, to move and phagocytose prey. The first description of amoebae was created by August Johann Rosel Von Rosenhof in 1755 (Von Rosen, 1755) . He named his discovery "Der Kleine Proteus" with illustrations showing an unidentified amoeboid, although with similarities to *Amoeba proteus*.

Initially named *Amoeba polyphagus*, *Acanthamoeba* was first isolated in dust by Puschkarew in 1913 (reviewed by Marciano-Cabral and Cabral 2003). The species' identification did not occur until 1930 when Castellani identified an amoeba of approximately 20 μM in size within a contaminated culture of *Cryptococcus pararoseus* (Castellani, 1930; Douglas, 1930). The newly discovered genus was named *Acanthamoeba castellanii* after Castellani. Following this *Amoeba polyphagus* was re-examined by Page and renamed *Acanthamoeba polyphaga* with *Acanthamoeba* being established as a genus by Volkonsky in 1931 (Page, 1967).

Acanthamoeba were initially thought to be benign, their potential for severe pathogenicity was not suspected until over twenty years later. In 1959 during attempts to identify unknown viral compounds found in test tissue samples Culbertson et al (Culbertson *et al.*, 1959) undertook routine animal pathogenicity tests. Sixteen monkeys received intracerebral, intraspinal and intramuscular injections of the unfiltered, undiluted and uncentrifuged tissue culture medium with 50 mg of cortisone acetate to prevent inflammation. All the monkeys died within seven days, autopsy showing both severe choriomeningitis and lesions at the site of injection; follow up tests with forty mice showed similar damage. Close examination showed unknown amoeba lying within the lesions and migrating through the tissue.

Culberston et al., proceeded to investigate the pathogenic potential of *Acanthamoeba* by injecting *Acanthamoeba* isolated from tissue samples, into mice and monkeys. With the results showing that direct injection of the amoeba proved to be pathogenic for mice with limited pathogenicity in the monkeys. Later his team reported seven fatal human cases of granulomatous amoebic encephalitis with amoebae similar to *A. castellanii*, confirming that *Acanthamoeba* is a potential human pathogen(Culbertson, Ensminger and Overton, 1966). The pathogenic potential of *Acanthamoeba* was further corroborated in the 1970s when improved diagnostic capabilities allowed for the reliable detection of *Acanthamoeba* spp. in cases of encephalitis, keratitis and cutaneous disease, with the number of reports increasing globally every year(Randag et al., 2019; Scruggs et al., 2019).

1.3 Environmental distribution

Acanthamoeba spp. are ubiquitous and have a worldwide distribution (Booton et al., 2005; Lass et al., 2017). An essential component of healthy ecosystem research has shown that *Acanthamoeba* is required to control bacterial and fungal populations in crops(Sinclair, McClellan and Coleman, 1981). Their role as secondary fermenters also renders them indispensable in this area, releasing minerals otherwise trapped within bacteria waste products into the surrounding environment (Rønn et al., 2002; Rosenberg et al., 2009) .

Acanthamoeba has been found near every ecosystem from the Arctic to the tropics that can support life (Shmakova and Rivkina, 2015). The species has been found to survive and replicate in hot springs and water heaters to temperatures as low as 10°C (Canals et al., 2015; Lares-Jiménez et al., 2018; Feiz Haddad et al., 2019). Combined with constant competition with other environmental pathogens, *Acanthamoeba* has evolved into a very robust species, shown by its difficult treatment(Larkin, Kilvington and Dart, 1992; Hay et al., 1994).

Water treatment regimens are currently incapable of removing the *Acanthamoeba* from water without potentially affecting its quality; leading to *Acanthamoeba* being frequent contaminants in tap water (Cervero-Aragó *et al.*, 2015). A small number of studies have been conducted to determine human exposure to *Acanthamoeba spp.* the most recent study, conducted in 2009 checked 114 asymptomatic individuals from 37 different countries and found that over 85% displayed antibodies against the amoeba (Brindley, Matin and Khan, 2009). An earlier study restricted to New Zealand showed all of the samples tested (Cursons *et al.*, 1980).

The diverse environments they colonise are unstable and have the potential to change rapidly from habitable to hostile (Takenouchi, Iwasaki and Murase, 2016; Feiz Haddad *et al.*, 2019). Adaption to these challenges required *Acanthamoeba* to evolve a two-stage life cycle; the active trophozoite feeding stage and the dormant, but significantly more robust, cyst stage (Figure 1.1).

The adaptability of *Acanthamoeba spp.* is their primary strength in their survival, regardless of even harsh environmental conditions. This same adaptability may also be the reason behind both *Acanthamoebas* capacity to be parasites. It can be argued that the majority of *Acanthamoeba* infections are due to the success of human medical intervention. There is a very low probability that an individual capable of developing GAE could survive outside the advantages of modern medication and while conditions for keratitis would emerge in the environment through injury or other infection contact lenses provide unique advantages to *Acanthamoeba* not found in the environment.

With these conditions required for infection there is little evidence of *Acanthamoeba* infection in the wild. Even if a wounded animal was infected with a particularly virulent strain

of *Acanthamoeba* spp. there is still the issue of transference. *Acanthamoeba* infection is debilitating, in wild conditions this weakness would rapidly lead to death through environmental factors or predators.

Neither of these routes offer a method to continue infection, outside of drowning there would be no way for amoeba to escape the carcass in sufficient quantities to continue their cell line. Death by predation also offers no infection route, to date there have been no reports of *Acanthamoeba* spp. infection through ingestion.

1.4 Life cycle

The majority of *Acanthamoeba* spp. have two primary stage in their life cycle, trophozoites and cysts, with *Acanthamoeba pyriformis* having a third sporocarp stage. Trophozoites are the active, feeding stage while cysts are an inactive, but highly robust and protective life stage (Bínová, Bína and Nohýnková, 2020).

Acanthamoeba spp. readily switch between the stages depending on adverse environmental factors including; pH, heat or pressure change, osmotic pressure or starvation (Gabriel and Panaligan, 2020) (Figure 1.1) .

Cyst formation has also been reported in isolated or highly confluent cells, likely due to the risk of adverse conditions or starvation, respectively. While the cyst stage is dormant, it continually monitors the environment until it is habitable once more, switching back to a trophozoite in a process termed excystation (Siddiqui *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 1.1: Life cycle of *Acanthamoeba* spp. showing the trophozoite, cyst and unique *A. pyriformis* sporulation stages (Scanning electron Micrograph taken by Dr. Lawrence Tetley, University of Glasgow).
Created with BioRender.com

1.4.1 Trophozoite stage

The trophozoite is the active stage of *Acanthamoeba* spp. life cycle, a relatively typical naked amoeba, is characterised by their distinct acanthopodia, very fine thorn-like pseudopodia that project from the cell's surface (Figure 1.1). The cell biology is consistent with the majority of eukaryotes, containing a Golgi complex, rough and smooth endoplasmic reticulum and mitochondria as well as. However, a large number of vacuoles for digestion and osmotic pressure regulation are frequently observed with lipid and polysaccharide reserves stored in the cytoplasm(Vickerman, 1962; Bowers and Korn, 1968), which is consistent with their life style.

While normally containing only a single nucleus, multinucleated trophozoite are a common observation in laboratory-grown trophozoites. Studies suggest this is an physical adaption to non-adherent conditions *Acanthamoeba* encounter as a part of their environmental distribution, with multinucleated cells producing more progeny than non-multinucleated cells. (James and Byers, 1967; Quinet *et al.*, 2020). Typically sizing from 12µM to 40µM, they are average in size when compared to another amoebae.

As the active life stage of *Acanthamoeba*, this stage is responsible for the direct damage associated with disease outcome, regardless of the site of infection. Their active metabolism also renders them far more vulnerable to treatment than their cyst form. Treatment of any *Acanthamoeba* infection can currently be described as attempting to either kill or inhibit the *Acanthamoeba* trophozoites before they are able to completely encyst, a process that can take as little as 48 hours(Bowers and Korn, 1969).

1.4.2 Encystment

The typical habitat of *Acanthamoeba* trophozoites is in the oxic layers of soils and sediments, conditions within these layers can change rapidly due to waterlog or turbulence, causing a rapid fluctuation of oxygen levels (Takenouchi, Iwasaki and Murase, 2016). While the trophozoites can adapt readily to most of these changes, normally within minutes; prolonged hypoxia, starvation or chemical stress will induce encystment (Aqeel *et al.*, 2013).

Encystment can be placed under three primary stages; pre-encystment, cyst initiation and cyst wall synthesis (Khunkitti, Lloyd, *et al.*, 1998). Pre-encystment changes are slight and are mostly indistinguishable from non-stressed trophozoites; the only major changes occur within the Golgi complex which distributes itself into smaller aggregates forming small vesicles and increasing in volume. Should conditions remain inclement, fibrillar materials are transported to the cell membrane and are used to form the primary components of the ectocyst. During this transport, the cell membrane gradually forms into a spherical shape with the membrane thickening. The fibrillar materials, primarily composed of cellulose, are used at this point to build the ectocyst. Simultaneously a significant increase in RNA and DNA levels relating to protein synthesis and membrane composition are affected, resulting in an increase in enzyme activity related to these systems (Bowers and Korn, 1969; Khunkitti, Hann, *et al.*, 1998; Chávez-Munguía *et al.*, 2005). Once ectocyst formation occurs, the endocyst is formed, and the cyst becomes metabolically inactive (Bowers and Korn, 1969).

1.4.3 Cyst Stage

The cyst is the dormant and metabolically inactive stage of the *Acanthamoeba* life cycle (Bowers and Korn, 1969). Highly resilient to even severe environments, having been found capable of lasting years without oxygen or food (Mazur, Hadas and Iwanicka, 1995). This resiliency carries on to treatment options, few compounds have been isolated that show significant effect against both stages of *Acanthamoeba* lifecycle (Coulon *et al.*, 2010).

Currently effective treatment options against cysts during *Acanthamoeba* keratitis infection cause significant discomfort to patients (Cristina, Cristina and Mihaela, 2016). The compounds, commonly a combination of a biocide and antifungal (Cristina, Cristina and Mihaela, 2016; Omaña-Molina *et al.*, 2019). The compounds are non-specific in action, limiting the concentrations that can be used without causing permanent damage to the patient during treatment.

As noted cysts are essentially a double-layered wall surrounding the inactive trophozoite (Bowers and Korn, 1969). The outer cyst wall is termed the ectocyst, exposed to the outside environment it generally is wrinkled with the folds containing large amounts of proteins and polysaccharides accounting for its robustness. The inner cell wall, the endocyst has far more variance in shape depending on the species of *Acanthamoeba* used (Page, 1981).

Composed mostly of cellulose the endocyst and exocyst are clearly separated and only meet at ostioles, these are holes within the cyst capped by a plug called an opercula. Once the environment becomes more hospitable, the opercula are pushed out of the cyst allowing the trophozoite to emerge. Cysts can take on three main shapes, stellate, oval or polygonal, when combined with size these distinct shapes were used before the advent of PCR to separate the species into their respective classes (M Pussard, R. Pons, 1977).

1.4.4 Excystation

In cyst form, *Acanthamoeba* are capable of surviving decades without food or water with some samples remaining viable from decade-old stock. While largely metabolically inactive the trophozoite within the cyst monitors the outside environment for more favourable conditions. Temperature, food and pH are all noted before the cell reactivates, potentially through ion transport channels (Siddiqui *et al.*, 2019).

Excystment begins with the cell rupturing the endocyst, after this, the cell removes one of the covers on an ostiole and emerges from the cyst as an active trophozoite.

1.5 Classification

Acanthamoeba are classified under the protozoan phylum Amoebozoa, forming the family Acanthamoebidae which includes *Protacanthamoeba* (Page, 1981) and the more recent identified *Dracoamoeba*, *Vacuolamoeba* (Tice *et al.*, 2016) and *Luapeleamoeba* (Shadwick *et al.*, 2016). With their broad, thick pseudopodia and lack of flagellate they belong to the discosea class of the lobosa subphylum (Cavalier-Smith, Chao and Oates, 2004).

Phylogenetic analysis of the Amoebozoa Super Group places it alongside metazoa and fungi, having branched out from a common ancestor (Baldauf *et al.*, 2000). This close relation provides advantages and disadvantages for treatment options of *Acanthamoeba* infections as similarities in biochemical pathways allow for a crossover of treatment options from one group to another. However, this comes at the cost of potential complications as the compound may have more severe side effects due to the similarity between the pathogen and the patient.

1.5.1 Groupings

Initially classified in 1931 using the older hierarchical system of classification, running the species through kingdom, phylum, subclass, order, family and genus. Older classification techniques required visual examination for distinct differences in grouping, however, as mentioned *Acanthamoeba spp.* trophozoites have no distinct differences between them. Once encysted however their morphology became distinct enough for morphological grouping, this began in 1977 when Pussard and Pons defined a classification system based upon the cysts' size and morphology classifying them into three groups I, II, III (M Pussard, R. Pons, 1977; Page, 1981).

Group I was defined as *Acanthamoeba* with large ($\geq 18 \mu\text{M}$) cysts with star-shaped endocysts and ectocysts with an alternating smooth and wrinkled appearance. Group II and Group III have similar sizes ($\leq 19 \mu\text{M}$) with Group II having polyhedral, globular, ovoid or stellate endocysts and ectocysts with a wavy appearance. Group III has cysts with globular or ovoid endocysts and smooth or wavy ectocysts. Using this old system Group II included the two most common pathogenic strains of *Acanthamoeba*; *A. castellanii* and *A. polyphaga*.

While providing a framework for classifying *Acanthamoeba* as a genus, the methodology used by Pussard and Pons had the same problems as any unquantifiable classification. The methodology itself was slow, required extensive expertise and has an inherent bias due to its purely observational reliance. Additionally, cyst morphology has been observed to change based on the growth medium used to further decrease this method's reliability (Stratford and Griffiths, 1978; Kliescickova, Kulda and Nohynkova, 2011).

In 1996, Gast et al., began work to reclassify *Acanthamoeba spp.* instead using 18s RNA gene sequences (Gast et al., 1996). The study set that a greater than 5% sequence in the highly

conserved regions in ribosomal DNA was required to be considered a new genotype of *Acanthamoeba* spp. This analysis showed the former system as incoherent, with some formal species such as *Acanthamoeba polyphaga* belonging to several distinct genotypes due to being polyphyletic (Corsaro *et al.*, 2017). Based on these assumptions, originally 17 genotypes of *Acanthamoeba* were established labelled T1 through T17b ribotype units. This has since increased to 22 genotypes (Corsaro, 2020).

The reclassification almost immediately showed clinical importance with the discovery that the majority of pathogenic *Acanthamoeba* spp. infections originate from the T4 ribotype. With the T4 genotype showing a greater overall virulence and a decreased susceptibility to established chemotherapeutic agents (Maciver *et al.*, 2013).

1.6 Pathogenesis of *Acanthamoeba* spp.

Acanthamoeba spp. cause two primary diseases, *Acanthamoeba* keratitis (AK) and Granulomatous Amoebic Encephalitis (GAE). A third rarer infection Cutaneous Acanthamoebiasis (CA) eventually ends in GAE. They are entirely opportunistic, while AK infection can occur in immunocompetent individuals; it is highly associated with contaminated contact lenses (González-Robles *et al.*, 2006). GAE and CA infections only occur in patients with immune disorders.

1.7 Granulomatous Amoebic Encephalitis (GAE)

Granulomatous Amoebic Encephalitis (GAE) is a rare, nearly always fatal form of encephalitis associated with immunocompromised patients (Łanocha-Arendarczyk *et al.*, 2018) or those suffering chronic disease. However, immunocompetent hosts have been reported (Das *et al.*, 2020). The infection is difficult to diagnose and generally only reported post-mortem, this is due to a combination of poor education of the disease and the rapid onset of symptoms. These factors may also have resulted in an underreported condition, particularly among transplant (Coven *et al.*, 2017) and older patients.

GAE is of growing concern, with increasing numbers of successful intervention in diabetes, AIDS and transplants, there is a growing number of patients becoming immunocompromised. Consequently, opportunistic pathogens such as *Acanthamoeba* spp. and their subsequent pathogenesis are drawing increasing interest, and funding, over the past few years.

1.7.1 Method of Infection

GAE infection begins when pathogenic *Acanthamoeba* gains access to the body, this is generally associated with contaminated water, e.g. swimming or bathing carrying amoeba to a cut or abrasion in the skin. Most of the reported cases of GAE are limited to individuals with a weakened immune system; chronic infections such as systemic lupus erythematosus (Grunnet, Cannon and Kushner, 1981; Thamtam *et al.*, 2016) HIV (Anzil *et al.*, 1991), diabetes and immunosuppressive therapy, generally for transplants (Anderlini *et al.*, 1994; Petry *et al.*, 2006)

Invasion of *Acanthamoeba* spp through the respiratory tract through alveolar blood cells has also been reported (Martinez, Markowitz and Duma, 1975). In immunocompetent individuals,

Acanthamoeba infection usually fails, with the immune system rapidly controlling the infection. In immunocompromised individuals, *Acanthamoeba* successfully begins to replicate and spreads to other tissues via haematogenous dissemination.

During this infection stage, amoebae invade the tissues and cause minor pathologies, including chronic sinus infections and skin lesions among other minor maladies. This stage of the disease can last for several months and, while severe, is the period where treatment can be successful if diagnosed early (Duarte *et al.*, 2006; Brondfield *et al.*, 2017). Eventually, however, *Acanthamoeba* will invade the CNS and breach the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and GAE will occur (Siddiqui *et al.*, 2011).

1.7.2 Pathogenesis

While the exact mechanisms that allow *Acanthamoeba* to breach the BBB and reach the CNS are not well understood, it is a slow and contract-driven process (Omaña-Molina *et al.*, 2017). The amoebae use Mannose-binding proteins (MPB) on their surface to attach to the surface of cells (Garate *et al.*, 2005), once attached *Acanthamoeba* release proteases into the surrounding environment. This weakens the tight junctions binding the BBB together through degradation of occluding and ZO proteins. *Acanthamoeba* then invades the weakened barrier consuming detached cells as a food source gaining access to the CNS (Omaña-Molina *et al.*, 2017).

Once the BBB is breached, the prognosis for the patient declines rapidly, and treatment becomes far more complicated as few effective treatments can bypass the BBB. Once the infection is established, GAE symptoms include migraines and mental degeneration due to neurological damage. Brain damage becomes more prevalent over time through a

combination of inflammation and *Acanthamoeba* feeding, although this is still being determined (Omaña-Molina *et al.*, 2017).

1.7.3 Treatment

Treatment of GAE is exceedingly difficult, the mortality rate exceeds 90%, and surviving patients often have neurological damage. Combined with a lack of awareness of both the disease and effective treatment, time is often lost with the treatment of other conditions.

Treatment consists of a multidrug regime that has includes; miltefosine, metronidazole, azithromycin, fluconazole, pentamidine isethionate, cotrimoxazole and ketoconazole with some success (Keane *et al.*, 2020). There is currently no set standard of treatment each depending upon the case, but overall, the probability of a positive disease outcome for GAE once *Acanthamoeba* have infiltrated CNS is poor.

1.8 Cutaneous Acanthamoebiasis (CA)

Cutaneous Acanthamoebiasis (CA) is isolated to the immunocompromised, though best documented in HIV/AIDS patients. However, the disease can also occur in transplant patients or patients with other immunological disorders to devastating effect. While considered uncommon, there is some evidence that poor diagnosis may be partially responsible for this (Torno *et al.*, 2000; Duarte *et al.*, 2006; Winsett *et al.*, 2017).

1.8.1 Pathogenesis

CA infection is identical to GAE, pathogenic *Acanthamoeba spp.* are introduced to the body through open wounds coming into contact with contaminated water (Walia *et al.*, 2007). Once introduced the amoebae begin to disseminate around the body through the bloodstream,

spreading throughout the body and can involve multiple organs including the skin, lungs and other visceral organs(da Rocha-Azevedo, Tanowitz and Marciano-Cabral, 2009).

The broad spectrum of effected organs can cause a considerable variation in symptoms rendering diagnoses a challenge. Lesions can include pustules, nodules, eschars, and papules typically focused on the extremities and face. However, this can be mistaken as symptoms from more commonly acknowledged diseases (Galarza *et al.*, 2009). Diagnosis relies on the visualisation of stained *Acanthamoeba* cysts and trophozoites, PCR and biopsy cultures.

Due to the nature of CA infection, the amoebae can eventually invade the central nervous system and cause GAE. CA infections that do not involve CNS invasion have a survival rate of approximately 73%. The mortality rate of CA with CNS invasion is currently 100% (Marciano-Cabral and Cabral, 2003).

1.8.2 Treatment

Once confirmed, treatment is aggressive, which can be problematic for already ill patients. One study successfully treated an HIV patient with CA using a multidrug treatment, including sulfadiazine. Other effective treatments include a combination of pentamidine, itraconazole with topical applications of ketoconazole and silver nitrate (Migueles and Kumar 1998) or a combination of 5-flucytosine, azithromycin, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, pentamidine, coriconazole and miltefosine (Visvesvara, Moura and Schuster, 2007).

1.9 *Acanthamoeba* keratitis

Acanthamoeba keratitis (AK) is a severe infection of the eye that affects 1 in 50,000 contact lens wearers (NHS, 2020). Characterised by severe pain, light sensitivity and sight loss the disease, while not ordinarily fatal, is nonetheless life-altering for the patient.

Unless quickly diagnosed and aggressively treated the infection will cause permanent damage to the eye, resulting in degradation of the patients' sight. An untreated infection will continue until the key has to be surgically removed via keratoplasty, once classified as a rare disease, the National Health Service (NHS) has reported a three-fold increase in the reported number of *Acanthamoeba* keratitis infections over the last decade (NHS, 2020).

1.9.1 Risk factors

Acanthamoeba keratitis (AK) is a progressive sight-threatening infection of the eye, currently requiring hospitalisation to properly treat with prognosis varying significantly based on numerous variables (Taravaud, Loiseau and Pomel, 2017; Thomson, Christopher A Rice, *et al.*, 2017). The majority of infections are caused by the T4 genotype, based on genetic analysis of samples taken from patients (Ledee *et al.*, 2009; Maciver *et al.*, 2013). This includes a multitude of *Acanthamoeba* species such as; *A. culberstoni*, *A. rhyodes*, *A. griffin* and most commonly *A. castellanii* and *A. polyphaga*.

Contact lens wear is considered a primary risk factor in AK development. By acting as both a point of entry for *Acanthamoeba* as the lens is easily bound to, and in addition, the lens acts as a physical barrier against mechanical detachment of the amoebae via blinking (Cristina, Cristina and Mihaela, 2016).

Contamination of contact lenses is associated with exposure to contaminated water, poor maintenance and biofilm formation. Swimming and showering with contact lenses have also been a risk factor (Taher *et al.*, 2017). Most of these issues can be solved through proper maintenance and following the user guidelines for contact lenses. However, currently, contact lens cleaning solutions are not required to be tested for efficacy against *Acanthamoeba* spp. and testing shows a distinct lack of effect (Johnston *et al.*, 2009). This lack of interest has been tied to multiple cleansing solution linked *Acanthamoeba* outbreaks (Verani *et al.*, 2009).

Once in contact with the cornea *Acanthamoeba* bind to surface glycoproteins using MBPs establishing infection. This binding is essential to the establishment of pathogenicity (González-Robles *et al.*, 2006). The inhibition of the MBP through α -mannose saturation was found to prevent binding of *Acanthamoeba* to corneal cells and significantly decreased pathogenicity of the infection (Garate *et al.*, 2005). While outside the scope of this study, the MBP may be a target of interest as a method of AK prevention, perhaps through addition to contact lens cleaning solutions.

1.9.2 Pathogenesis

The complete mechanisms behind AK's pathogenesis are not completely understood, current understanding points to the amoeba releasing a plethora of digestive enzymes; cysteine proteinases, fibrinolytic enzymes, and phospholipases. One study comparing non-pathogenic and pathogenic *Acanthamoeba* shows these enzymes are more active in pathogenic strains. This is reinforced through additional studies showing similar correlations in pathogenicity of protozoans strains such as *Trypanosoma cruzi*.

The cornea is composed of a closely-knit layer of cells, tightly bound by specialised binding proteins. The release of the digestive proteins has a devastating effect on this layer. The released enzymes destroy the binding proteins between cells, separating cells and making consumption by *Acanthamoeba* easier via phagocytosis. The resultant necrosis also results in inflammation, resulting in sensitivity and severe pain for the patient.

1.9.3 Treatment

Acanthamoeba keratitis is an arduous, time-consuming and varies considerably depending on location and individual medical practitioners practice. In the UK standard treatment consists of hourly doses of a combination of a biguanide, including polyhexamethylene biguanide (PHMB) or chlorhexidine combined with a diamidine such as propamidine (Larkin, Kilvington and Dart, 1992; Omaña-Molina *et al.*, 2019).

These treatments are given hourly for the first 48 hours, requiring waking of the patient during the night, before being reduced to once hourly only during waking hours over a two-week timeline. Treatment then decreases to every two hours during waking hours for another month, monotherapies are still used, generally with lesser effect.

While effective, these treatments are toxic to the patients' cornea and tend to result in discomfort to the patient, combined with the lack of rest and maintenance of the treatment can become problematic. This is problematic as should treatment fail then the only effective treatment methods left are surgical, with keratoplasty and enucleation of the eye being treatments of last resort (Kitzmann *et al.*, 2009).

Treatment of AK is further complicated with hostile environments inducing *Acanthamoeba* to encyst. Once fully encysted *Acanthamoeba* become resistant to treatment, and the amoeba

are capable of surviving up to 31 months after initial therapy before excystation. With some species capable of surviving over thirty thousand years in permafrost (Shmakova and Rivkina, 2015). Additionally, the cysts can cause inflammation due to shedding antigens, resulting in prolonged irritation for the patient before treatment ends and the amoeba can re-establish infection.

1.10 Challenges in the treatment of *Acanthamoeba* infections

With current medical technology, few diseases in the world are all but incurable, CA and GAE fall under this category. Additionally, infection rates may be higher than reported due to diagnosis frequently only occurring post-mortem (Thamtam *et al.*, 2016).

The current treatment regimens lack consistency in efficacy against infection, cysts further this issue through turning effective treatment into a timed event. For GAE treatment, the lack of effective compounds that can also cross the BBB renders effective treatment difficult (Salameh *et al.*, 2015b).

Together these factors render more effective treatments essential, while undoubtedly rare sufferers of CA and GAE already have compromised immune systems and require rapid, effective treatment to ensure survival (Walia *et al.*, 2007; Keane *et al.*, 2020). AK, while non-lethal, is nevertheless life-changing for those infected, with even prompt treatment still resulting in permanent damage to the eye. Current treatment regimens currently give medical practitioners little time to diagnose a rare condition and engage in treatment that is arduous on the patient.

Currently, three significant challenges are facing the development of more effective *Acanthamoeba spp.* treatment. The first challenge is essential knowledge, like most

opportunistic pathogens *Acanthamoeba spp.* rarely attracts public attention, with news of its sporadic outbreaks often diverted by outbreaks of *N. fowleri*. This lack of knowledge is found within the medical field itself and is at least partly to blame for frequent misdiagnosis (Carnt *et al.*, 2018; Lee *et al.*, 2020). As an example, AK is frequently initially treated as a bacterial infection, a significant issue as standard bacterial treatment often encourages amoebal growth.

The second challenge is tied to the first, lack of knowledge of *Acanthamoeba spp.* and its subsequent infections leads to a difficulty in getting funding for studies. This lack of financing tends *Acanthamoeba spp.* studies towards smaller overall studies resulting in slower progress in treatment development. Lack of funding also renders the creation of entirely *de-novo* treatments difficult with the current preferred method of drug discovery being through redeployment of compounds developed for similar, more popular, organisms.

The third challenge is linked into the biochemical similarity between *Acanthamoeba spp.* and human cells. Both species are eukaryotes and as such rely on the same biochemical pathways, unlike with bacteria or virus. Meaning that toxicity is a concern when examining potential treatment (Baldauf *et al.*, 2000).

1.11 Novel and experimental treatments

With an acknowledgement of these restraints, the most effective method of creating new, improved treatments would be through a combination of utilising already available treatments and finding synergistic interaction between the most effective compounds.

For example, the characterisation of the sterol biochemistry pathway has determined a valid drug target in *Acanthamoeba spp.* This is based on the biochemical similarity between fungi

and *Acanthamoeba spp.* and the ease with which antifungals can be utilised against *Acanthamoeba spp.* infection. Additionally, the pathway has several advantages for potential synergistic interaction. The pathway is linear, with several key enzymes that are currently utilised as drug targets and inhibition of the pathway has been shown to have amoebicidal capabilities (Thomson, Christopher A Rice, *et al.*, 2017).

Currently, the primary focus of most studies is the azoles, 14- α -demethylase inhibitors with a good record of *Acanthamoeba spp.* treatment. Additionally, statins, HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors have also been shown to have an effect against *Acanthamoeba* (Martín-Navarro *et al.*, 2013) However, few studies attempt to use these compounds in combination (Sifaoui *et al.*, 2019), and so far, there are no studies to determine if these compounds enhance the capability of the biocides used in current treatment regimens.

1.11.1 Exploration of synergy between drugs of different classes

Almost the entirety of successful in-vivo *Acanthamoeba spp.* treatment relies on an aggressive multidrug approach (Cristina, Cristina and Mihaela, 2016; Keane *et al.*, 2020). However, it has only been recently that studies have focused on exploring these combinations *in-vitro* (Silva *et al.*, 2020), with a current focus on the combination of sterol inhibitors being the current focus.

While there are some claims of success to these treatments (Roze and Linz, 1998; Silva *et al.*, 2020) there is currently a massive dearth of information on the current most potent treatment. Consisting of a combination of sterol inhibitors to weaken the membrane and biocides that directly interact with the weakened membrane.

Improving or broadening knowledge of how these combinations interact would both be a great boon to treatment knowledge and would also potentially provide a starting point for a standardised *Acanthamoeba spp.* treatment. Furthermore, as the biocide, in the case of AK, is the primary point of irritation for the patient a greater understanding of sufficient concentrations in combination may allow for a decrease in concentration and so a less difficult time for the patient.

A primary challenge in dealing with eukaryotic pathogens is to avoid having the drug also affect host cells' similar biochemistry. However, Sterol inhibitors are commonly used in medicine for various conditions, so their toxicity in humans is well understood (Endo, 2003).

More practical, and more importantly, better-understood treatments of *Acanthamoeba spp.* are essential for the effective treatment of all pathologies of *Acanthamoeba*. The sterol biosynthesis pathway allows for the exploration of several drug targets while simultaneously

rendering the amoeba vulnerable to synergistic interaction from compound affecting additional enzymes within the pathway as well as compounds directly effecting the weakened membrane. Additionally, there is some information suggesting that the disruption of sterol biosynthesis may increase the time taken for encystment rendering these compounds a vital addition to *Acanthamoeba* treatment.

Sterols are a diverse range of organic molecules, a subgroup of steroids they occur naturally in plants animals, fungi and some bacteria. Typically known for their role in membrane stability, sterols are essential in a variety of roles from cell signalling to components in sebum.

The sterol membrane composition of *Acanthamoeba* spp. offers a weakness that is not shared with human cells. There are three primary sterols used depending on species, animals use cholesterol, fungi ergosterol and plants use phytosterols, with a preference for stigmasterol.

Of clinical interest to this study is that, unlike human cells, *Acanthamoeba* spp. uses ergosterol as its primary membrane support lipid while human cells use cholesterol.

1.12 Aims and Objectives

Previous studies have shown repeatedly that the sterol biochemical pathway is a viable drug target in *Acanthamoeba* spp. Clinical studies continuously show that combination therapy is a critical feature in the treatment of *Acanthamoeba* infection. However, few studies explore the relationship between these two essential treatment options *in-vitro*. Additionally, there are other potential treatment options under these families that have not been explored.

The aims of the studies described in this thesis can be divided into two primary goals with several smaller objectives. Initially my aim is to expand on current treatment options through the exploration of sterol inhibitors. Including characterising their synergistic capability with

characterise their synergy with biocides and each other. This would allow for a significantly more in-depth understanding of effective treatment options for *Acanthamoeba* keratitis in particular but may elucidate further treatment options for the far more lethal GAE. To build on this, a series of squalene epoxidase inhibitors have to date never been employed against *Acanthamoeba spp.* making this thesis the first to utilise these compounds as both a monotherapy and as part of combination therapy.

My secondary aim is to develop new analytical tools for exploration of *Acanthamoeba spp.* interaction with effective compounds. This will be carried out in two ways, utilising Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry to confirm and analyse the effect of the sterol inhibitors on treated *Acanthamoeba spp.* sterol biosynthesis pathway. Additionally this thesis will aim to create a fluorescent cell line of *Acanthamoeba spp.* this would allow for the creation of a fluorescent drug assay eliminating the need for expensive reagents. With the further goal to utilise the developed methodology as a testbed for the development of a CRISPR-Cas9 cell line of *Acanthamoeba spp.* allowing for rapid genetic modification of *Acanthamoeba spp.*

This project is an opportunity to contribute to the understanding of this understudied organism and to also assist in the development of more effective treatments to a currently devastating disease.

Chapter 2 **Materials and Methods**

2.1 *Acanthamoeba* spp. and Isolates

Two isolates of *Acanthamoeba* spp., obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) were used for comparative results. ATCC 50370 (ATCC 50370) an *Acanthamoeba castellanii* strain and ATCC 50371 (ATCC, United States) an *Acanthamoeba polyphaga* strain.

2.2 Growth and Harvesting of *A. castellanii* and *A. polyphaga* Trophozoites

All *Acanthamoeba* spp. were initially grown in a nutrient rich media (NRM) (Table 2.1), the media was later switched to PG media and all recorded experiments were carried out using this media. The media of isolates Neff, Clinical T4 and ATCC 50370 were supplemented with 1% 125 µg penicillin/streptomycin (Sigma, Poole, United Kingdom) with isolate Neff being further supplemented with 1% 125 µg amphotericin B (Sigma, Poole, United Kingdom). Unless stated otherwise all isolates were grown at room temperature in 75 cm² tissue culture flasks (Corning, Amsterdam, The Netherlands). The trophozoites were passed on a 4/3 day cycle, harvested via mechanical detachment and collected in a 50 ml centrifugation tube (Corning, Amsterdam, The Netherlands) by centrifugation at 1200 g for 5 minutes forming a pellet.

2.3 *Acanthamoeba* spp. Passage

Acanthamoeba spp. were grown and harvested according to section 2.2 the used media was discarded; 10 ml of pH 7 phosphate buffer solution was added to the 50 ml centrifugation tube and the pellet was put back into solution through repeat pipetting. The trophozoites were then collected by centrifugation at 2100 rpm at 4°C for 5 minutes. The PBS was discarded, and the pellet was re-suspended in 1ml PG media. 100µl of the suspension was added to 10ml of Protease Peptone/Glucose medium (Table 2.2) for all isolates.

2.4 Optimal Seeding density

Previously *Acanthamoeba spp.* were optimised for the AlamarBlue™ assay, final cell numbers are shown below.

Table 2.1: Table showing selected seeding densities for the AlamarBlue™ Assay at 24 and 96 hours.

Time (hours)	ATCC 50370 (Cells/Well)	ATCC 50371 (Cells/Well)
24	2×10^4	2×10^4
96	2×10^3	2×10^3

2.5 Media Preparation

2.5.1 Protease Peptone/Glucose (PG Media)

Table 2.2: Composition of the Protease Peptone/Glucose (PG) Media. Table does not include a salt solution that has to be added separately.

Glucose (Alfa Aesar, UK)	15	g/L
Protease Peptone (Sigma, UK)	15	g/L
KH ₂ PO ₄ (Sigma, UK)	0.3	g/L
Thiamine (Sigma, UK)	0.001	g/L
L-methionine (Sigma, UK)	0.0149	g/L
B12 (Sigma, UK)	83.3 µl	0.1 mg/ml
Biotine (Sigma, UK)	83.3 µl	0.2 mg/ml

Table 2.3: Composition of the Salt Solution for PG Media

CaCl ₂ ·H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	0.15	g/100 ml
FeCl ₃ (Sigma, UK)	0.02	g/100 ml
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	2.46	g/100 ml

1 ml/L of the salt solution was added to the media stock prior to autoclaving.

2.5.2 M20 Defined Media

M20 media was prepared in three separate stages prior to autoclaving; Amino acids and trace elements were prepared together, 6 salt solutions were prepared and autoclaved separately from each other, Glucose and Vitamins were added after autoclaving.

Table 2.4: Amino acids and Trace elements used in preparing M20 media. Table does not show the Salts and Vitamins that were prepared and added separately.

Amino Acids			
Arginine·HCl (Sigma, UK)	825	mg/L	Alanine (Sigma, UK) 1050 mg/L
Glycine (Sigma, UK)	1500	mg/L	Asparagine (Sigma, UK) 495 mg/L
Isoleucine (Sigma, UK)	600	mg/L	Aspartic Acid (Sigma, UK) 750 mg/L
Leucine (Sigma, UK)	900	mg/L	Glutamic Acid (Sigma, UK) 1500 mg/L
Lysine (Sigma, UK)	1250	mg/L	Proline (Sigma, UK) 60 mg/L
Methionine (Sigma, UK)	300	mg/L	Serine (Sigma, UK) 1050 mg/L
Valine (Sigma, UK)	700	mg/L	Cysteine (Sigma, UK) 75 mg/L
Threonine (Sigma, UK)	500	mg/L	Tyrosine (Sigma, UK) 60 mg/L
Histidine·HCl·H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	160	mg/L	Glutamine (Sigma, UK) 14.6 mg/L ¹
Phenylalanine (Sigma, UK)	900	mg/L	
Tryptophan (Sigma, UK)	200	mg/L	
Trace Elements			
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	1	mg/L	CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O (Sigma, UK) 0.0033 mg/L
MgCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	2.3	mg/L	H ₃ BO ₃ (Sigma, UK) 0.1 mg/L
(NH ₄)Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	0.4	mg/L	Na ₂ EDTA (Sigma, UK) 0.01 mg/L
CaCl ₂ (Sigma, UK)	0.17	mg/L	

¹. Due to its short half-life in solution glutamine was added directly before the media was to be used

Table 2.4.1: Salt solutions were prepared separately from each other in 100ml of distilled water. An additional 100 ml of distilled water was also prepared

Salts	
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	985 mg/L
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	58.8 mg/L
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ FeSO ₄ ·6H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	19.6 mg/L
Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·2H ₂ O (Sigma, UK)	445 mg/L
K ₂ HPO ₄ (Sigma, UK)	340 mg/L
Sodium Citrate (Sigma, UK)	1000 mg/L
Distilled Water (Sigma, UK)	100 ml

Table 2.4.2: Vitamins and Glucose were added to 100ml of pre-autoclaved distilled water.

Biotin (Sigma, UK)	0.25 mg/L
B12 (Sigma, UK)	0.00125 mg/L
Thiamine (Sigma, UK)	1.25 mg/L
Glucose (Alfa Aesar, UK)	36000 mg/L

All solutions were then filter sterilised and added to the medium. M20 media is acidic and had to be neutralised back to pH7 using twice filter sterilised 1M NaOH before use.

2.5.3 Encystment Media

Table 2.5: Salts used to create *Acanthamoeba* spp. encystment media

Tris-HCL (Sigma, UK)	2.4 g/L
KCl (Sigma, UK)	7.46 g/L
MgSO ₄ (Sigma, UK)	0.96 g/L
CaCl ₂ (Alfa Aesar, UK)	0.04 g/L
NaHCO ₃	0.08 g/L

2.6 Azole Drug Preparation

2.6.1 Tioconazole

0.38771 g of Tioconazole (Sigma, UK) was dissolved in 1 ml of DMSO a 1 in 31.25 dilution was then carried out using PG media giving a cloudy solution, the pH of the media was then lowered to pH 1.8 which caused the media to clear. A 1 in 63 dilution was then carried out to give a final concentration of 250 μM .

2.6.2 Voriconazole

0.01 g of Voriconazole (Tocris, UK) was dissolved in 1ml of DMSO, a 1 in 200 dilution gave a final concentration of 143 μM .

2.7 Biocide Preparation

2.7.1 Chlorhexidine

1mg of Chlorhexidine (Sigma, UK) was dissolved in 1ml of water for a stock concentration of 400 mM. 200 μl of the stock was then added to 9800 μl of PG media to give a final concentration of 40 μM . The stock was then diluted to a final stock of 20 μM .

2.7.2 Polyhexamethylene biguanide (PHMB)

1mg of Polyhexamethylene biguanide (Carbosynth, UK) was dissolved in 1ml of water for a stock concentration of 4.7 mM. 50 μl of the stock was then added to 4950 μl of PG media to give a final concentration of 47 μM . This was then diluted to 31.2 μM .

2.8 Squalene Epoxidase Inhibitor Preparation

2.8.1 Amorolfine

5 mg of amorolfine (Sigma, UK) was dissolved in 1ml of DMSO for a stock concentration of 14.13 mM.

25 μ l of the stock was then added to 4975 μ l of PG media to give a final concentration of 70.65 μ M.

2.8.2 Butenafine

10 mg of Butenafine (Sigma, UK) was dissolved in 1 ml of DMSO for a stock concentration of 28.25

mM. 15 μ l of the stock was then added to 4985 μ l of PG media to give a final concentration of 85 μ M.

2.8.3 Naftifine

25 mg of Naftifine (Sigma, UK) was dissolved in 1ml of ethanol for a stock concentration of 77.19

mM. 7 μ l of the stock was added to 4993 μ l of PG media for a concentration of 108 μ M.

2.8.4 Terbinafine

30 mg of Terbinafine (Sigma, UK) was dissolved in 1 ml of Ethanol for a stock concentration of 91.4941

mM. 12.5 μ l of the stock was then added to 4987.5 μ l of PG media for a final stock concentration of

228.74 μ M

2.9 Statin Preparation

2.9.1 Atorvastatin

5 mg of Atorvastatin (Sigma, UK) was dissolved in 500 μ l of DMSO for a stock concentration of 16.54 mM. 25 μ l of the stock was then added to 4975 μ l of PG media to give a final concentration of 83 μ M.

2.9.2 Lovastatin

5 mg of Lovastatin (Santa Cruz, USA) was dissolved in 500 μ l of DMSO for a stock concentration of 24.72 mM. 50 μ l of stock was then added to 4950 μ l of PG media to give a final concentration of 248 μ M.

2.9.3 Mevastatin

5 mg of Mevastatin (Sigma, UK) was dissolved in 250 μ l of DMSO for a stock concentration of 51.22 mM. 12.5 μ l of the stock was then added to 4987.5 μ l of PG media to give a final concentration of 128.13 μ M.

2.9.4 Simvastatin

5 mg of Simvastatin (Sigma, UK) was dissolved in 250 μ l of DMSO for a stock concentration of 47.78 mM. 12.5 μ l of the stock was then added to 4987.5 μ l of PG media for a concentration of 119.5 μ M

2.9.5 Pitavastatin

10 mg of Pitavastatin (Santa Cruz, USA) was dissolved in 1ml of DMSO for a stock of 23.72 mM. 25 μ l of the store was then added to 4975 μ l of PG media for a concentration of 114 μ M

2.10 alamarBlue™ Assay

2.10.1 Calculating alamarBlue™ Reduction Compared to Control

The percentage reduction of alamarBlue™ (AbD Serotec, UK) compared to the control was calculated using the following equation:

$$(Y * T_1) - (X * T_2) / (Y * C_1) - (X * C_2) * 100$$

Whereby X is the molar extinction coefficient (E) of oxidised alamarBlue™ at 570nm (80568); Y is the E of oxidised alamarBlue™ at 600nm (117216); T₁ is the absorbance of the test wells at 570nm; T₂ is the absorbance of the test wells at 600nm; C₁ is the absorbance of the control wells at 570nm; C₂ is the absorbance of the control wells at 600nm. The results obtained were then multiplied by 100 and averaged to give the percentage difference in reduction from test wells to control. Background reduction caused by the media was accounted for by subtracting the average reduction of alamarBlue™ caused by the media from all results and then dividing the new results of the test wells by those of the control. For clarity purposes, the positive control, trophozoites with media alone unless stated otherwise, was set to 100% with all other results compared.

2.10.2 alamarBlue™ Drug Assay

After the drug sample had been prepared (Section 2.5), the sample was serially diluted. 50 µl of each sample was added to a 96 well tissue culture plate, in triplicate, 50 µl of media containing the appropriate number of trophozoites for the isolate and time-point. Controls consisted of; the PG blank, trophozoites with media alone, trophozoites with the highest concentration of solvent, and media with the highest concentration of drug alone. The final volume of all wells was 100 µl. The plates were then incubated at 23.3°C until 6 hours before the time-point that was being measured, the plate was removed from the incubator, and 10 µl of alamarBlue™ reagent was added to one of the columns for each of the mediums, the plate was then incubated at 23.3°C for a further 6 hours in the dark. The

absorbance was then read on a spectromax (Molecular Devices, US) spectrophotometer at OD₅₇₀ and OD₆₀₀.

2.11 Optimisation and initial testing of GC-MS sterol extraction protocol

2.11.1 Sterol extraction

2.10.1.1 Cell preparation

8×10^6 *Acanthamoeba* were pelleted by centrifugation at 1,200 g for 5 minutes. The media was then discarded, and the cells resuspended in 1 ml PBS, resuspended, and centrifuged again at 1,200 g for 5 minutes. The PBS was then discarded, and the samples allowed to air-dry for 5 minutes.

2.10.1.2 Sterol extraction kit

Cells were suspended in 1 ml methanol. The cells were centrifuged again at 1,200 g for 5 minutes and the methanol mostly discarded. The cells were resuspended in the remaining methanol and then added to 3ml of extraction solvent. The sample was then homogenised and vortexed, 0.5 ml of aqueous buffer was added, and the mixture was vortexed. The entire mixture was poured into the supplied syringe and the lower chloroform phase was collected.

2.10.1.3 Sterol extraction without kit

8×10^6 *Acanthamoeba* were pelleted by centrifugation at 1,200 g for 5 minutes. The media was then discarded and 5 ml of a 1/1 chloroform/(90% methanol, 10% water) mix was added. The cells were then transferred to a clean glass vial and left overnight at 4 °C. The cells were homogenised and the lower chloroform containing layer of approximately 2.5 ml was transferred to a clean glass tube. Additional chloroform was then added, and the cells homogenised again, this was repeated twice more accounting for a total of 10 ml of chloroform being extracted. The chloroform solvent was then evaporated, and the lipids reconstituted with 500 µl of chloroform prior to being analysed.

2.11.2 GC-MS Sample preparation

2.10.2.1 Derivatization

Sterol sample was mixed with BSTFA (N,O-Bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide) in a 1:1 ratio. The mix was then heated at 50°C for 1 hour then allowed to cool. The mixture was then evaporated using nitrogen and resuspended in chloroform.

2.10.2.2 Solid Phase Extraction

A C18 column (Agilent, UK) was conditioned by adding 1ml of methanol, running it through and repeating the process. The sample was then added and ran through the column, the column was washed using 2ml of water and then allowed to dry for 20 minutes. The sterols were collected by adding 1ml of chloroform and collecting the sample in a vial.

2.10.2.3 Evaporation

The complete sterol extract was allowed to dry overnight at room temperature, then resuspended in 1ml of chloroform.

2.11.3 GC-MS protocols

2.10.3.1 Sterols 1

Sterols 1 was based on the protocol used in (Thomson, Christopher A Rice, *et al.*, 2017). The presence of steroids was analysed on a Thermo Finnigan Polaris Plus GCMS. Initial temperature was at 100 °C, initial time of 1.00 min, with 1 ramp at a rate of 20.0 deg/min to a final temperature of 320 °C. The column was an Agilent HP-5ms (5%-phenyl)-methylpolysiloxane) GC column.

2.10.3.2 Sterols 2

Sterols 2 was based on the protocol used in (Zhou *et al.*, 2018). The initial temperature was 170°C for 1 minute, with a ramp of 20°C to a final temperature of 280°C and held for 2 minutes for a

final runtime of 20 minutes. The column was an Agilent HP-5ms (5%-phenyl)-methylpolysiloxane) GC column.

2.10.3.3 Sterols 3

The extract was analysed on an Agilent technologies 5975C series GC/MSD system (Agilent, UK). The initial temperature was 100°C for 1 minute, with a ramp of 5°C to a final temperature of 300°C and held for 2 minutes for a final runtime of 43 minutes. The injection volume was 5 µl, the column was a thermos scientific TRACE TR-5MS (5% Phenyl polysilphenylene-siloxane) GC column.

2.12 Enzyme Restriction Digest

Restriction digests were carried out in total volumes of 100 µl per digest. Each reaction volume contained 15 µl of the plasmid, 10 µl 10X buffer and 2.5 µl of the enzyme, the mix was then topped up to 100 µl with distilled, autoclaved water (ddH₂O). The reaction mix was then incubated overnight at 37°C.

Once the digest was complete test runs of the products, containing 5 µl of product, 10 µl of ddH₂O and 1.5 AP loading dye were then run on a 0.8% agarose gel stained with 7 µl of ethidium bromide (Sigma, UK) the gel then underwent electrophoresis at 120 V for 45 minutes and was visualised on a transilluminator. Upon successful digest, 10 µl of AP loading dye was added to the reaction mix and the entire mix was run on an agarose gel as described above.

2.12.1 pBAExpress Restriction Digest

Due to buffer incompatibility, the pBAexpress had to undergo a two-step digest. BglIII (NEB, UK) was used as described in 2.7.4 with 10X buffer 3.1 (NEB, UK). After a successful test digest, the reaction mix was run through a PCR clean-up protocol as described in 2.12.3

After successful clean up the product was digested with NheI (NEB, UK) in 10X buffer 2.1 as described in 2.12.

2.12.2 pBBSDRFPCSV40 Restriction Digest

pBBSDRFPCSV40 restriction digest was carried out as described in 2.7.4 with BglIII (NEB, UK) and XbaI (NEB, UK) in 10X buffer 3.1 (NEB, UK).

2.12.3 Extraction of Product Following Gel Electrophoresis

After electrophoresis, the gel was viewed on a transilluminator the products of the successful digests were excised from the gel with a sharp, clean scalpel. The product extraction was completed using a NucleoSpin® Gel and PCR clean-up kit (Macherey-Nagel,UK) the according to the manufacturer's instructions. The gel fragments were placed in a 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube and the fragment itself was weighed through calibrating the scale with an empty 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube. Two volumes of Buffer NTI were added to one volume of gel. The solution was incubated at 50°C until the gel fragment was completely dissolved. The mixture was then transferred to a NucleoSpin® Gel and PCR Clean-up column. A series of centrifugation, wash and elution steps allowed for the DNA to be bound to and eluted from the silica-gel-membrane in the NucleoSpin® Gel and PCR Clean-up column.

PCR clean-up was identical to the extraction protocol with the only difference being the use of the PCR reaction compared to gel fragments.

2.12.4 SAP treatment of pBAExpress product

As prevention against spontaneous relegation 1.2 µl of ddH₂O, 6.8 µl cutsmart x10 buffer (NEB, UK) and 2 µl SAP (NEB,UK) was added to the pBAExpress gel extract product. The mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 2 hours and then the SAP denatured by incubating the mix at 65 °C for 30 minutes.

2.12.5 Ligation of gene products

The ligation reaction was carried out in a total volume of 15 µl. The reaction contained 1 µl of pBAExpress digest, 6 µl of pBBSDRFPCSV40 digest, 1.5 µl T4 ligase buffer (NEB, UK) and 0.8 µl T4 ligase

(NEB, UK) topped to 15 μl with ddH₂O. The reaction was then left overnight at 13 °C with a successful ligation generating the new plasmid pBASV40GFP.

2.12.6 Transformation

4 μl of the plasmid was added to 100 μl of competent *E. coli* (NEB, UK) in a microcentrifuge tube and then placed on ice for 1 hour. The reaction mix was transferred to a 42 °C water bath for 90 seconds and then placed on ice for a further 5 minutes. 800 μl of LB medium was added to the sample and the mix was incubated at 37 °C for 1 hour with shaking. The sample was then plated onto two LB agar plates containing 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ampicillin at volumes of 100 μl and 200 μl . The plates were incubated at 37 °C overnight, six surviving colonies were then selected from the plate and were transferred, aseptically, to six 10 ml of LB media with 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ carbenicillin (Sigma, UK). The samples were then incubated at 37 °C overnight.

2.12.7 TENS-CO Mini-prep

Before the TENS procedure was carried out a sample from each of the overnights was plated onto an LB plate using a sterile loop.

After the creation of a backup 1.5 ml of each overnight culture was added to a 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube and spun down at 15800 g for 30 seconds. The supernatant was removed, and the cells re-suspended in the remaining supernatant. 300 μl of buffer 10mM Tris-HCl (Sigma,UK), 1mM EDTA (Sigma,UK), 150mM NaCl (Sigma,UK) and 0.5% SDS (Sigma,UK) (TENS) was added and the cell suspension vortexed at medium speed for 4 seconds then immediately placed on ice. 150 μl of 3M Sodium acetate (Sigma, UK) (pH 5.2) was added the suspension was vortexed again at medium speed for 3 seconds and then placed on ice.

The suspension was then centrifuged at 15800 g at 4°C for 10 minutes and the supernatant was transferred to a fresh 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube. This was repeated until the supernatant was

particulate-free typically taking around 2-3 attempts. 900 µl of ice-cold 100% ethanol was added. The mixture was vortexed and then centrifuged at 15800 g at 4°C for 15 minutes.

The supernatant was removed, and the DNA pellet washed with 1ml of ice-cold 70% ethanol and centrifuged at 15800 g at 4 °C for 10 minutes. The supernatant was then completely removed, and the pellet allowed to dry for 15 minutes before being dissolved in 40 µl of ddH₂O.

2.12.8 pBASV40GFP Test Digest

4 µl of each miniprep product was added to a 15 µl reaction mix containing 1.5 µl buffer 3.1, 0.3 µl NcoI (NEB, UK), 0.1 µl RNase A (NEB, UK) topped up to 15 µl with ddH₂O. The reaction mix was then incubated for 3 hours at 37 °C before being run on a 0.8% agarose gel for 45 minutes at 120 V. The gel was then viewed on a transilluminator and a colony from the mini-prep product that showed the correct fragment pattern was then aseptically transferred to 100 ml of LB broth containing 100ug/ml carbenicillin.

2.12.9 Midiprep

The Midi prep was carried out using a NucleoBond® Xtra Midi kit (Macherey-Nagel, UK) according to the manufacturer's instructions. In brief 100ml of the overnight culture was re-suspended in an RNase A containing buffer and then lysed, a series of wash and elution steps allowed the DNA to be to and eluted from the Midi-prep column. To avoid contamination of the DNA during the last wash step the 70% ethanol was removed and the pellet dried under a hood. The pellet was then re-suspended in ddH₂O that had been filter-sterilised.

2.12.10 Midi prep test digest

Restriction digests were carried out in reaction mixes of 15 µl containing 0.3 µl enzyme, 1 µl Midi prep sample DNA, 1.5 µl buffer topped up to 15 µl with ddH₂O. The enzymes AvrII (NEB, UK) with cutsmart® buffer, BglII and NcoI both with buffer 3.1 were used for the test. Once prepared the reaction mix was left overnight at 37 °C.

2.12.11 Transformation of *Acanthamoeba castellanii* Neff strain

The transformation of *Acanthamoeba* Neff was carried out by Xfect™ transfection kit (Takara, France), *Acanthamoeba* Neff was cultured as previously explained, 5×10^5 cells were pelleted, washed with encystment media and then suspended in 500 μ l encystment media and the cells were then transferred to a six-well culture plate.

5 μ g of DNA was added to a microcentrifuge tube, Xfect Reaction Buffer was then added to give a total volume of 100 μ l and mixed by vortex for 5 seconds. 1.5 μ l of pre-vortexed Xfect Polymer Reagent was then added, and the solution was mixed via vortex for 10 seconds, the solution was then centrifuged to collect the contents and incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature.

The entire solution was added to the cell culture, after which the plate was rocked to mix the contents. 700 μ l of encystment medium was then added to the cells, giving a final volume of 1200 μ l.

Two reaction mixes were made, plate one was incubated with the transfection solution for 4 hours at room temperature after which the solution was carefully removed via pipette and then replaced with 4 ml of PG media. Plate two was incubated with the reaction mix for 24 hours before having it removed and the PG media added. Both plates were left for 24 hours following the addition of the PG media to allow for the cells to recover, 1ml of PG media was then added as well as the selection marker G418 at a final concentration of 28.07 μ M. The cells were incubated at room temperature for two weeks allowing for cell selection to occur.

After successful resistance was found, the cells were grown to confluence before being passes as previously described, with the plasmid being maintained through constant pressure using 28.07 μ M G418.

2.12.12 Fluorescent Microscopy

To increase the copy number of pBASV40GFP resistant *Acanthamoeba* from both the 4 and 24-hour transfection were each split into 3 T25s containing 10ml of PG media and 28.07, 54.14 and 84.21 μ M

of G418. The cells were spun down at 2,500 rpm for 5 minutes, and the media was removed. The cells were resuspended in 1 ml of PG media, and 25 μ l of cells was placed on a microscope slide. The cells were examined on a Nikon Eclipse 600 Epifluorescent Upright Microscope (Nikon, USA) under a wavelength of 475 nm to excite the GFP and determine if it was expressed within the cell.

Chapter 3 Squalene Epoxidase as a drug target in
Acanthamoeba spp.

3.1 Sterol Biosynthesis

Sterol biosynthesis is a complex multi-step process, the pathway is a branch of the mevalonate pathway from which squalene, the critical component of the pathway, originates. Sterol biosynthesis begins with the conversion of squalene into squalene-2,3-epoxide through catalytic conversion by squalene epoxidase (Figure 1).

End-point sterols differ between species and can be generalised; cholesterol is found in mammals, ergosterol in fungi and stigmasterol in plants. Despite the differences, end-point sterols have similar properties, the molecules are responsible for membrane stability, but also have roles in membrane signalling and oxidation protection (Brown and London, 1998). Disruption of sterol biosynthesis is therefore, catastrophic for cell viability in any species (RYDER, 1992).

Figure 3.1: Simplified sterol Biosynthesis pathway showing the chemical structure of Cholesterol, Ergosterol and Stigmasterol as well as their universal precursor Squalene.

3.2 Targeting Sterol Biosynthesis in *Acanthamoeba spp.*

Acanthamoeba spp. are known to produce ergosterol and 7-dehydrostigmasterol as their primary membrane sterols (Smith & Korn, 1968). Previously it has been found that compounds commonly used as antifungals have a significant effect against *Acanthamoeba spp.* Currently, the most used compounds belong to the 'azole' group, which are the standard therapy against fungal infections (Thomson, et al. 2017).

Voriconazole has been successfully used in clinical settings against *Acanthamoeba spp.* that display resistance to standard treatments of chlorohexidine and polyhexamethaline biguanide (Hou, Chen and Hsu, 2017). Voriconazole binds to and inhibits the third enzyme in the sterol biochemical pathway, lanosterol 14- α -demethylase. This enzyme converts lanosterol into 4,4-dimethylcholesta-8,(9),14,24-trien-3 β -ol through demethylation.

Inhibition of these enzymes leads to a build-up of toxic intermediaries and reduces the levels of free end-point sterols available to the cells. These combined effects lead to cell death, either through toxin build-up or cell rupture due to membrane weakening. Similarly, the use of voriconazole on *Acanthamoeba castellanii* and *polyphaga* results in a build-up of lanosterol and a decrease in ergosterol; suggesting a similar mechanism of action (Thomson, et al. 2017)

3.3 Squalene Epoxidase

Inhibition of sterol biosynthesis is a potent target in *Acanthamoeba spp.* for drug development. Our hypothesis is that other antifungal compounds with differing target enzymes may also show *Acanthamoeba spp.* inhibition.

Located on the endoplasmic reticulum, squalene epoxidase catalyses the first oxygenation step in sterol synthesis, introducing an epoxide group into the isoprenoid squalene to form squalene-2,3-epoxide. This step is a requirement for the folding of the isoprenoid into either lanosterol or cycloartenol depending on species. Lanosterol is then used to produce cholesterol or ergosterol, cycloartenol produces stigmasterol. (Brown, Chua and Yan, 2019)

Like lanosterol-14- α -demethylase, squalene epoxidase is a well-established target in antifungal therapy. This has allowed for the identification of five well-established antifungals that target squalene epoxidase.

3.3.1 Inhibitors

Amorolfine, Butenafine, Naftifine, Terbinafine and Tolnaftate (Figure 2) are all known inhibitors of squalene epoxidase (Bhattacharya, Sae-Tia and Fries, 2020). Tolnaftate is a synthetic thiocarbamate, while the other four belong to the allylamine family of medications (Georgopapadakou and Bertasso, 1992).

The compounds are frequently used against fungal species including *Candida spp.*, *Trichophyton spp.* and *Epidermophyton spp.* amongst others (Salehi, Shams-Ghahfarokhi and Razzaghi-Abyaneh, 2018; Gnat *et al.*, 2020; Shaw *et al.*, 2020). Fungal strains are developing resistance to these compounds however, with overexpression of squalene epoxidase or mutation of the drug binding site significantly increasing the effective concentration of SQE inhibitors (Taghipour *et al.*, 2020).

An additional attraction to these compounds is their potential for synergy with the lanosterol 14- α -demethylase inhibitors. Inhibition of squalene epoxidase and the subsequent lanosterol-14- α -demethylase should decrease free ergosterol levels further than either alone.

Further, these compounds are all well-established medications in humans, with well-known toxicities. Terbinafine is on the WHO essential medicines list and considered one of the most crucial antifungals in the world. These criteria fit well with the overall goal of this thesis; repurposing of medication against *Acanthamoeba spp.* and their deployment into the clinic(Sacheli *et al.*, 2020).

Amorolfine

Butenafine

Naftifine

Terbinafine

Tolnaftate

Figure 3.2: Molecular Structure of the five selected anti-fungals that will be used in this study.

3.4 Aims and Objectives

Despite the highly conserved nature of squalene epoxidase, there have been no studies conducted in its potential as a drug target in *Acanthamoeba spp.* Herein, the hypothesis that squalene epoxidase inhibitors may inhibit *Acanthamoeba* growth is explored. Additionally, inhibition of both the lanosterol 14- α -demethylase and squalene epoxidase may have a more significant overall effect than the inhibition of either alone.

Therefore, the primary aims of this chapter are to determine the effectiveness of squalene epoxidase inhibition against *Acanthamoeba spp.* using test strains *A. castellanii* (ATCC 50370) and *A. polyphaga* (ATCC 50371) trophozoites. Selected compounds will then be used as part of a multidrug study with established compounds from the 'azole' group. This will allow for the determination of synergy or antagonism between the compounds.

3.5 Results

3.5.1 Inhibition of Squalene Epoxidase inhibits the growth of multiple isolates of

Acanthamoeba spp. in vitro

Optimal seeding density for Alamarblue reduction was assessed previously (Table 3.1), trophozoites were harvested, and dilutions were seeded on a 96 well plate. The plates were incubated for 24 and 96 hours, 6 hours before the plate reached its time of initial incubation the plate was removed from the incubator and 10 μ l of alamarBlue reagent was added. The plate was read using a spectromax spectrophotometer at OD₅₇₀ and OD₆₀₀, results were calculated using equations provided by the manufacturer.

The effect of squalene epoxidase inhibitors was assessed using a modified version of the alamarBlue™ microtiter plate assay, as described by (McBride *et al.*, 2005). A complete summary of the results is shown in Table 1.

Terbinafine was the most effective inhibitor tested; showing inhibition at 24 hours with an IC₅₀ of 16.4 μ M for *A. castellani* and 12.46 for *A. polyphaga*. Terbinafine was more effective at 96 hours with an IC₅₀ of 4.01 μ M for *A. castellani* and 6.8 μ M for *A. polyphaga*. (Figure 2.7 and 2.8)

Terbinafine was also the only inhibitor to show an IC₉₀; at a concentration of 38.15 μ M for *A. castellani* and 44.7 μ M for *A. polyphaga*. Amorolfine was the second most effective inhibitor with an IC₅₀ of 6.95 μ M for *A. castellani* and 7.07 μ M for *A. polyphaga*. Tolnaftate was the least effective drug tested showing no significant inhibitory effect at either timepoint. Microscopic investigation showed no amoebicidal activity of either squalene epoxidase inhibitor; suggesting amoebastatic capability.

Figure 3.3: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Amorolfine ($35.50 \mu\text{M}$ – $0.07 \mu\text{M}$). Controls consisted of a positive without Butenafine control, a solvent control and media with Amorolfine alone ($42.5 \mu\text{M}$). Amorolfine has an inhibitory effect at concentrations $\geq 17.75 \mu\text{M}$ at 24 hours, and $\geq 2.22 \mu\text{M}$ 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 3.4: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Amorolfine (35.50 μM – 0.07 μM). Controls consisted of a positive without Butenafine control, a solvent control and media with Amorolfine alone (35.50 μM). Amorolfine has an inhibitory effect at concentrations $\geq 4.44 \mu\text{M}$ at 24 hours, and $\geq 1.11 \mu\text{M}$ 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 3.5: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Butenafine ($42.5 \mu\text{M} - 0.08 \mu\text{M}$). Controls consisted of a positive without Butenafine control, a solvent control and media with Butenafine alone ($42.5 \mu\text{M}$). Butenafine has an inhibitory effect at concentrations $\geq 5.31 \mu\text{M}$ at both 24 hours, and 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 3.7: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 503701 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with Butenafine (42.5 μM – 0.08 μM). Controls consisted of a positive without Butenafine control, a solvent control and media with Butenafine alone (42.5 μM). Butenafine has an inhibitory effect at concentrations ≥ 5.31 μM at 24 hours and ≥ 21.25 at 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 3.8: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Naftifine (54 µM – 0.11 µM). Controls consisted of a positive without Naftifine control, a solvent control and media with Naftifine alone (54.00 µM). Naftifine has an inhibitory effect at concentrations ≥ 3.38 µM at both 24 hours, and 13.5 µM at 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 3.9: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with Naftifine ($42.5 \mu\text{M} - 0.08 \mu\text{M}$). Controls consisted of a positive without Naftifine control, a solvent control and media with Naftifine alone ($54.00 \mu\text{M}$). Naftifine has an inhibitory effect at concentrations $\geq 3.38 \mu\text{M}$ at both 24 hours and $6.75 \mu\text{M}$ at 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 3.10: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Terbinafine (114.5 µM – 0.22 µM). Controls consisted of a positive without Terbinafine control, a solvent control and media with Terbinafine alone (114.5 µM). Terbinafine has an inhibitory effect at concentrations ≥ 3.58 µM at 24 hours, and 1.79 µM 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 3.11: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Terbinafine (114.5 µM – 0.22 µM). Controls consisted of a positive without Terbinafine control, a solvent control and media with Terbinafine alone (114.5 µM). Terbinafine has an inhibitory effect at concentrations ≥ 3.58 µM at 24 hours and ≥ 0.89 at 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 3.12: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Tolnaftate (410 µM – 0.80 µM). Controls consisted of a positive without Tolnaftate control, a solvent control and media with Tolnaftate alone (410 µM). Tolnaftate has no inhibitory effect at the concentrations tested. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity

Figure 3.13: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Tolnaftate (410 µM – 0.80 µM). Controls consisted of a positive without Tolnaftate control, a solvent control and media with Tolnaftate alone (410 µM). Tolnaftate has no inhibitory effect at the concentrations tested. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

3.5.2 Results Summary

Table 3.2: Table summarising the IC₅₀ and IC₉₀

Amorolfine:	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	6.95 µM	1.02	N/A	N/A
ATCC 50371	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	7.07 µM	4.60	N/A	N/A

Butenafine	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	14.60 µM	3.10	N/A	N/A
ATCC 50371	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Naftifine	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	49.65 µM	0.77	N/A	N/A	24.50 µM	8.80	N/A	N/A
ATCC 50371	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	16.25 µM	3.00	N/A	N/A

Terbinafine	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	16.40 µM	5.50	N/A	N/A	4.01 µM	1.13	38.15 µM	7.80
ATCC 50371	12.46 µM	2.98	N/A	N/A	6.80 µM	1.30	44.70 µM	8.65

Tolnaftate	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATCC 50371	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

3.5.3 Squalene Epoxidase Inhibitors do not show significant synergistic capability with 14- α -demethylase inhibitors

Terbinafine was established as the most effective Squalene epoxidase inhibitor tested. Subsequently, it was used as the test drug for testing for potential synergy with 14- α -demethylase inhibitors. The effect of the combined drug solutions was assessed using a modified version of the alamarBlue™ microtiter plate assay adapted for multidrug use.

The synergistic effect was determined through Combenifit™ using Loewe Additivity as a reference model. Terbinafine was tested with Tioconazole and Voriconazole two of the most effective azoles previously found. However, no synergistic effect was found, the results instead suggest additivity.

Figure 3.14: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Tioconazole (7.8 μM - 0.49 μM) and Terbinafine (4.02 μM - 0.25 μM) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$

Figure 3.15: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Voriconazole ($0.5 \mu\text{M}$ - $0.03 \mu\text{M}$) and Terbinafine ($4.02 \mu\text{M}$ - $0.25 \mu\text{M}$) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$

3.6 Discussion

This chapter characterises the capabilities of five squalene epoxidase inhibitors against the two pathogenic species of *Acanthamoeba* (*A. castellanii* and *A. polyphaga*). The inhibitors examined (Amorolfine, Butenafine, Naftifine, Terbinafine and Tolnaftate) have anti-*Acanthamoeba* activity; this is likely through the inhibition of ergosterol synthesis via squalene epoxidase inhibition.

Microscopic analysis showed none of the inhibitors tested showed any amoebicidal capabilities; however, three of the inhibitors (amorolfine, naftifine and terbinafine) showed good amoebastatic effect at the 96-hour mark. The IC_{50} of *Acanthamoeba spp.* is almost universally higher than that of non-resistant fungi strains against the inhibitors used. This matches previous studies showing a marked increase in required concentration for an IC_{50} to be achieved in *Acanthamoeba spp.* compared to fungi.

A possible explanation for this is that, while highly conserved, there will be structural differences between fungal and *Acanthamoeba spp.* squalene epoxidase. It is these differences that allow for preferential binding to fungi rather than humans. Similarly, structural differences may result in incomplete or partial binding of the compound resulting in less effective activity in *Acanthamoeba spp.* against fungi (Konc, Lešnik and Janežič, 2015).

There is little information available about the precise mechanism of action of the allylamines. Their capability to inhibit squalene epoxidase is well established as a family; however, less is known about individual compounds. Naftifine has been found to inhibit in a non-competitive manner, terbinafine however is thought to have competitive inhibition (Ryder and Dupont, 1985; Castberg, Helle and Aamo, 2005). These methods of inhibition are radically different and may explain the differences in their subsequent activities.

Terbinafine as a competitive inhibitor would bind to the enzyme's active site or an area close to the active site. These areas are highly conserved and thus would be relatively similar between fungi and

Acanthamoeba spp. As a non-competitive inhibitor naftifine would bind to an area outside of the active site, these areas would be more open to mutation and so less active due to structural differences.

Determining the direct effect of these compounds would require isolating *Acanthamoeba spp.* squalene epoxidase and testing the effect the inhibitors have on the enzymes V_{\max} and K_m values, using squalene as the substrate and detecting squalene-2,3-epoxide levels. Once determined, V_{\max} and K_m values would allow for identifying the method of inhibition each compound uses.

To date there have been no assays of this type carried out in *Acanthamoeba spp.*, doing so may allow for a significant increase in our knowledge of how these compounds are interacting with *Acanthamoeba spp.* compared to their more well-established mechanism of action in fungi.

As noted, none of the compounds have comparable IC_{50} to their effect in fungi. Amorolfine has activity in the nanomolar range against the fungus *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (Gnat *et al.*, 2020). Butenafine has a MIC of $\sim 6.3\mu\text{M}$ against a range of dermatophytes (Salehi, Shams-Ghahfarokhi and Razzaghi-Abyaneh, 2018). Naftifine surprisingly showed a greater effect against *Acanthamoeba spp.* (IC_{50} 16.25-24.5 μM) than it currently does against some strains of *T. mentagrophytes-interdigitale*, which have an IC_{50} of $>50\mu\text{M}$ (Shaw *et al.*, 2020). Tolnaftate was included in this study to give perspective on the potential of Squalene epoxidase inhibitors outside of the allylamine family. However, it was found to have no activity against the *Acanthamoeba spp.*, in high contrast to an IC_{50} of ~ 195.17 nM against clinical dermatophyte isolates (Baghi *et al.*, 2016; Abastabar *et al.*, 2019).

This study has confirmed that squalene epoxidase is a viable drug target in the treatment of opportunistic infections caused by *Acanthamoeba spp.* Terbinafine was the most active compound found with a low IC_{50} but like the other effective allylamines was only amoebastatic instead of amoebicidal. This was followed by Amorolfine with Naftifine showing the next most effective inhibition, butenafine only found an IC_{50} with one strain. It, therefore, was considered less effective despite its technically lower concentration than naftifine.

Reasons for *Acanthamoeba spp.* survival of treatment could have numerous, combined reasons. Terbinafine is a competitive inhibitor; however, these types of inhibitors rely on binding to and blocking the active site of an enzyme. As the substrate builds up in the surroundings, these inhibitors become less effective simply due to the probability of the inhibitor binding before the substrate dropping over time (Konc et al., 2015). While naftifine would not have this issue, as a non-competitive inhibitor, a structural change could decrease its overall effect, this is a noted mechanism of fungal resistance (Rudramurthy et al., 2018). As such while drug concentrations may reach sufficient levels to achieve inhibitory effect *Acanthamoeba spp.* may have defences or enzyme structural changes that prevent the inhibitors from reaching lethal concentrations.

Similarly, the other allylamines would have similar issues, our emerging hypothesis, therefore, was that inhibiting both squalene epoxidase and lanosterol 14- α -demethylase would have a synergistic effect. If the allylamines were simply being overwhelmed by substrate, or enzyme upregulation, then inhibiting a close enzymatic step would prevent any lanosterol produced from being converted to 4,4-dimethylcholesta-8(9),14,24-trien-3 β -ol, and so to ergosterol and 7-dehydrostigmasterol.

However, our data does not support this hypothesis, most telling was the terbinafine with tioconazole study. Neither of these compounds are amoebicidal on their own. Where our hypothesis correct then we would have seen an apparent increase in effect, if not through our activity assay then through direct observation. However, the data instead shows that each compound works on an individual level, with no detectable overlap in drug activity.

The lack of interaction is interesting, although not uncommon, synergistic interaction is complex and rarely functions according to predicted models. However, as has been noted, lanosterol 14- α -demethylase is only two steps down from squalene epoxidase (Figure 2). As such upregulation of both enzymes, combined with eventual substrate saturation, may simply render any combined effect inert. A 24-hour study may allow for this effect to be observed, before any potential substrate build-up, but was not conducted during this study.

The next step, therefore, would be to block an enzyme further upstream from our current target to see if this effect could be overcome. Recently 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-glutaryl-coenzyme A reductase (HMGCR) has become a target of some interest in *Acanthamoeba spp.* treatment (Martín-Navarro *et al.*, 2013). Five statins, inhibitors of HMGCR have been selected for effect and will be used in the next study.

Overall, this study has proven that squalene epoxidase is a viable drug target in parasitic *Acanthamoeba spp.* The study has also shown that *Acanthamoeba spp.* display near-universally increased resistance to these compounds when compared to their effects in fungi. The research has also shown that there is no synergistic, or antagonistic, effect between azoles and terbinafine. This study demonstrates that Amorolfine and Terbinafine, in particular, show functional inhibition against both isolates and thus may prove beneficial as part of a treatment course.

Chapter 4 **HMG-CoA reductase as a drug target in**

Acanthamoeba spp.

4.1 Mevalonate pathway

The mevalonate pathway is an essential metabolic pathway present in archaea, bacteria and eukaryotes, and is responsible for cholesterol production in humans. The mevalonate pathway has a crucial role in multiple cellular processes, such as sterol biosynthesis, but also is critical in the production of non-sterol isoprenoids including dolichol, heme-A isopentenyl tRNA and ubiquinone (Rohmer *et al.*, 1996; Boucher, Kamekura and Doolittle, 2004).

The pathway is separated into the upper pathway, consisting of the first three enzymatic reactions, and the lower pathway which differs between species. The upper pathway is highly conserved and starts with the introduction of acetyl-CoA as a carbon stock and ending with the production of (R)-mevalonate. The lower pathway varies depending on species, but has the same endpoint, with the output of Isopentenyl pyrophosphate (IPP) and dimethylallyl pyrophosphate (DMAPP) (Figure 1).

Figure 4.1 Upper and lower mevalonate pathway, showing the Eukaryotic, Archaea I and Archaea II generic pathways for the production of IPP and DMAPP.

4.1.1 Mevalonate pathway inhibition

Inhibition of the mevalonate pathway has multiple consequences, depending on species and drug concentration. In humans, the pathway is targeted as a method of lowering cholesterol concentration to decrease the risk of cardiovascular disease (Kwak *et al.*, 2019). Dysregulation of the mevalonate pathway has been linked with cancer risk and is a target of interest in cancer therapy (Di Bello *et al.*, 2020). Of most significant interest to this study, the mevalonate pathway has been shown as an antimicrobial target in fungi (Brilhante *et al.*, 2020)(Brilhante *et al.*, 2020). This research led to an interest in the potential of the mevalonate pathways potential as a target in anti-acanthamoeba therapy, which has been successfully demonstrated (Martín-Navarro *et al.*, 2013).

The primary method of inhibition of the mevalonate pathway is the inhibition of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA reductase (HMG-CoA reductase; HMGR) (Endo, 2003). Inhibition of this enzyme reduces the production of mevalonate and reduces overall production of end-sterol products in the affected organism (Endo, Kuroda and Tsujita, 1976).

4.2 HMG-CoA reductase

The mevalonate pathway is responsible for the production of cholesterol in humans and is linked to cardiovascular disease. Found on the surface of the endoplasmic reticulum, HMGR is the rate-controlling enzyme of the mevalonate pathway (Toyota *et al.*, 2020). It is the third enzyme of the pathway and the final enzyme of the upper mevalonate pathway; it is highly conserved throughout the phyla and it reduces HMG-CoA to mevalonate by NADPH. Mevalonate is subsequently converted to IPP or DMAPP through the lower mevalonate pathway (Figure 1).

As the rate-limiting step in the pathway, HMGR has been a primary drug target as a method of regulation. Discovered in 1973, statins are reversible competitive inhibitors of HMGR and one of the most prescribed medications in the world (Endo, Kuroda and Tsujita, 1976; Kwak *et al.*, 2019).

4.2.1 Statins

Statins are reversibly competitive inhibitors of HMGR, binding to the HMGR active site without undergoing any reaction. The active site of the statins occupies the HMG portion of the HMG-CoA binding pocket, additional non-polar regions block the area of the coenzyme-A binding site preventing further reaction (Figure 2).

The first statin was isolated from the fungi *Penicillium citrinum* during a wide-spectrum search for compounds that inhibited lipid synthesis. ML-236B, later mevastatin, was eventually found to have suitable characteristics, including lowering plasma cholesterol in patients with hypercholesterolemia (Yamamoto, Sudo and Endo, 1980). A second statin, lovastatin was isolated shortly after and was put forward as the first clinically accepted statin after mevastatin was linked to intestinal tumours in animal studies (Endo, 2004).

Statins are generally grouped according to their structure, type 1 statins are statins that resemble mevastatin, due to their structural relationship. This group also have to be hydrolysed through enzymatic reactions to their active form. Type 2 statins are fully synthetic and are designed to have a greater resemblance to HMG; additionally, these compounds use polar interactions to amplify their binding to HMGR. These statins are active from the outset and require no additional activation steps (Hamelin and Turgeon, 1998) (Figure 2).

While best known for their role in cholesterol regulation, statins have noted antifungal and anti-acanthamoebic activity (Roze and Linz, 1998; Martín-Navarro *et al.*, 2013). Like with previously tested anti-fungals this is likely due to binding differences due to enzyme structural differences.

Figure 4.2: Figure shows molecular structure of three type 1 statins (Lovastatin, Simvastatin and Mevastatin) and two type 2 statins (Atorvastatin and Pitavastatin) and the HMG-CoA substrate. Highlighted area shows characteristic butyryl group of type 1 statins and the fluorophenyl group of type 2 statins.

4.3 Mevalonate pathway in *Acanthamoeba* spp.

Previously we have established that the sterol biosynthesis pathway is a valid target in *Acanthamoeba* spp. However, we were unable to obtain synergistic interactions with already used compounds.

HMGR has previously been recorded as an effective target in *Acanthamoeba* spp. with several statins showing inhibition (Martín-Navarro *et al.*, 2013). Expanding upon this research would allow for further elucidation on potential drug candidates for *Acanthamoeba* spp. In addition, the species used in this thesis are different from those previously used. Additionally, there is evidence of drug synergy between azoles and statins against *Candida* spp. (Silva *et al.*, 2020) which is encouraging for our own search for synergy against *Acanthamoeba* spp.

To this goal, we have selected five statins, Atorvastatin, Lovastatin, Mevastatin, Pitavastatin and Simvastatin. All are well-established inhibitors of HMGR and will be used as a part of this assay, atorvastatin, lovastatin and simvastatin have previously been found to be used in previous therapy (Martín-Navarro *et al.*, 2013). However, mevastatin and pitavastatin have not been tested for anti-*acanthamoeba* capabilities. Knowledge of already effective inhibitors will allow for the synergy study going forward even should we find a lesser inhibitory effect in the strains used in this study. There is some evidence that fungi excrete statins as a method of defence against other fungi and so this study will also be looking into the differing effects of Type 1 statins against Type 2 (Boruta, Milczarek and Bizukojc, 2019).

4.4 Aims and Objectives

In the previous chapter, it was established that allylamines showed inhibitory effect against *Acanthamoeba spp.* in line with our hypothesis of crossover effects. However, synergy could not be determined with previously tested azoles. Statins have already shown a synergistic effect with several azoles against *Candida spp.* while also showing functional inhibition as a single drug treatment.

The primary aims of this chapter are to determine the effectiveness of statins, HMGR inhibitors against *Acanthamoeba spp.* *A. castellani* ATCC 50370 and *A. polyphaga* ATCC 50371. The compound with the most significant inhibitory effect against *Acanthamoeba spp.* will then be used as part of a multidrug study with established azoles and Terbinafine to determine the potential for synergy through inhibition of both the precursor mevalonate pathway and the sterol biosynthesis pathway.

This study's objective is to assess the inhibitory capabilities of five selected HMGR inhibitors, the rate-limiting enzyme of the mevalonate pathway. The most effective inhibitor will then be evaluated for its potential in combination therapy.

4.5 Results

Using a previously standardised cell number (Table 4.1), HMGR inhibitors' effect was assessed using a modified version of the alamarBlue™ microtiter plate assay as described by (McBride *et al.*, 2005). A complete summary of the results is shown in Table 3

Both Atorvastatin and Pitavastatin showed good effect against both strains of *Acanthamoeba*. Pitavastatin was shown to be the most effective inhibitor tested overall, showing inhibition at 96 hours with an IC₅₀ of 2.29 µM and an IC₉₀ 8.27 µM for *A. castellanii* 50370. *A. polyphaga* 50371 showed an increased sensitivity compared to 50370 with an IC₅₀ of 0.91 µM and an IC₉₀ of 4.61 µM. Notably, pitavastatin showed direct cell death when directly observed with a microscope for both strains in comparison to atorvastatin.

Levostatin, Mevastatin and Simvastatin showed no effect at the concentrations tested against either strain at either 24 or 96 hours.

Figure 4.3: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Atorvastatin (41.50 µM – 0.08 µM). Controls consisted of a positive without Atorvastatin control, a solvent control and media with Atorvastatin alone (41.50 µM). Atorvastatin has an inhibitory effect at concentrations ≥ 5.19 µM at 24 hours, and 2.59 µM at 96 hours ($P < 0.05$). Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 4.4: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with Atorvastatin ($41.50 \mu\text{M} - 0.08 \mu\text{M}$). Controls consisted of a positive without Atorvastatin control, a solvent control and media with Atorvastatin alone ($41.50 \mu\text{M}$). Atorvastatin has an inhibitory effect at concentrations $\geq 5.19 \mu\text{M}$ at both 24 hours, and 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 4.5: 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Lovastatin (123.5 µM – 0.96 µM). Controls consisted of a positive without Lovastatin control, a solvent control and media with Lovavastatin alone (123.5 µM). Lovastatin had no inhibitory effect at 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 4.6: 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with Lovastatin (123.5 µM – 0.96 µM). Controls consisted of a positive without Lovastatin control, a solvent control and media with Lovavastatin alone (123.5 µM). Lovastatin had no inhibitory effect at 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 4.7: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Mevastatin (64 μM – 0.13 μM). Controls consisted of a positive without Mevastatin control, a solvent control and media with Mevastatin alone (64.00 μM). Mevastatin had no inhibitory effect at 24 or 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 4. 4.82×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with Mevastatin (64 µM – 0.13 µM). Controls consisted of a positive without Mevastatin control, a solvent control and media with Mevastatin alone (64.00 µM). Mevastatin had no inhibitory effect at 24 or 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 4.9: 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Pitavastatin (56.75 μM – 0.44 μM). Controls consisted of a positive without Mevastatin control, a solvent control and media with Mevastatin alone (56.75 μM). Pitavastatin had an inhibitory effect at concentrations ≥ 1.77 μM at 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 4.10: 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with Pitavastatin (56.75 μM – 0.44 μM). Controls consisted of a positive without Mevastatin control, a solvent control and media with Mevastatin alone (56.75 μM). Pitavastatin had an inhibitory effect at concentrations ≥ 0.89 μM at 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 4.11: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* were seeded in PG media with Simvastatin (59.5 μM – 0.12 μM). Controls consisted of a positive without Simvastatin control, a solvent control and media with Simvastatin alone (59.50 μM). Simvastatin had no inhibitory effect at 24 or 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

Figure 4.12: 2×10^4 (24 Hours) or 2×10^3 (96 Hours) trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with Simvastatin (59.5 μM – 0.12 μM). Controls consisted of a positive without Simvastatin control, a solvent control and media with Simvastatin alone (59.5 μM). Simvastatin had no inhibitory effect at 24 or 96 hours. Each value represents the mean of triplicate wells \pm SEM, assay was carried out in duplicate, single representative run shown for clarity.

4.5.1 Results Summary

Table 4.2: Table summarising the IC₅₀ and IC₉₀

Atorvastatin:	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	9.32 µM	0.34	N/A	N/A	6.22 µM	0.94	27.99 µM	2.10
ATCC 50371	4.24 µM	1.20	N/A	N/A	6.80 µM	1.13	29.74 µM	2.44

Levostatin	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATCC 50371	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Mevastatin	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATCC 50371	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Pitavastatin	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.29 µM	0.29	8.27 µM	1.28
ATCC 50371	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.91 µM	0.06	4.61 µM	0.21

Simvastatin	24 Hours	SE		SE	96 Hours	SE		SE
Isolate	IC₅₀	IC₉₀			IC₅₀	IC₉₀		
ATCC 50370	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATCC 50371	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

4.5.2 Statins do not show significant synergistic capability with 14- α -demethylase inhibitors or Squalene Epoxidase inhibitors.

Of the statins available at the time, atorvastatin was established as the best inhibitor to use in the synergy assay. Consequently, it was chosen as the test drug for testing for potential synergy with 14- α -demethylase inhibitors as well as terbinafine. The effect of the combined drug solutions was assessed using a modified version of the alamarBlue™ microtiter plate assay adapted for multidrug use.

Atorvastatin was not found to have any synergistic effect with either of the azole inhibitors tested at 96 hours. The synergistic effect was determined using Combenifit™ using Loewe Additivity as a reference model.

Figure 4.13: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Tioconazole (62.5 μM - 3.90 μM) and Atorvastatin (35.68 μM - 2.23 μM) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$

Figure 4.14: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Voriconazole ($4 \mu\text{M}$ - $0.25 \mu\text{M}$) and Atorvastatin ($35.68 \mu\text{M}$ - $2.23 \mu\text{M}$) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$

Figure 4. 1.52×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Terbinafine (32.16 μM - 2.01 μM) and Atorvastatin (35.68 μM - 2.23 μM) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$

4.6 Discussion

This chapter characterises the capabilities of five 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-glutaryl-CoA reductase inhibitors, statins, against two pathogenic strains of *Acanthamoeba spp.* (*A. castellani* and *A. polyphaga*). The inhibitors examined (Atorvastatin, Lovastatin, Mevastatin, Pitavastatin and Simvastatin) express anti-*Acanthamoeba* activity; likely through inhibition of ergosterol synthesis via HMGR inhibition.

Of the inhibitors tested, only pitavastatin showed amoebicidal capabilities, of the other compounds only atorvastatin showed an inhibitory effect. None of the Type 1, naturally derived statins, showed any effect against the *Acanthamoeba* strains used in this study. There may be multiple explanations for this, the type 1 statins used in this assay were in their prodrug form when added into the assay following the methodology suggested in (Martín-Navarro et al., 2013). While activity was achieved in the previous study, the strains used in this study may not be able to hydrolyse the statins, blocking activity. However, this hydrolysis capability was not explored in Martín-Navarro et al., (2013). This could be rapidly solved by incubating the statins in a NaOH-ethanol mixture before use in the assay. While planned time constraints, unfortunately, stopped this assay from being carried out.

Furthermore, while clinically used in the regulation of cholesterol production, there is little doubt that fungi have evolutionary pressures to produce statins. Statin concentrations are effected during co-culture of fungi, which combined with their antifungal, antibacterial and antiviral effects suggests that statins are used as a method of defence (Boruta et al., 2019). If this being the case, *Acanthamoeba spp.* being readily found in the environment would regularly encounter statins during competitive growth with fungi and may have defence mechanisms in place to defend itself.

The differences in the capabilities between atorvastatin and pitavastatin are of interest. While both inhibited *Acanthamoeba spp.* pitavastatin showed far greater inhibitory effect than atorvastatin, including amoebicidal capabilities. This may be linked to previous studies showing that statins are capable of inducing apoptosis in *Acanthamoeba spp.* atorvastatin may be only inhibiting HMGR

without inducing apoptosis unlike pitavastatin (Martín-Navarro et al., 2015). Alternatively, pitavastatin may have a greater binding efficiency than atorvastatin, this would increase the length of time it would take for substrate overexpression to start overwhelming the statin levels. The increased time would perhaps allow for the increased effectiveness of the compound.

As highlighted in the previous chapter in the context of allylamines an enzyme binding assay could be carried out to clarify the nature of pitavastatin's capabilities over atorvastatin. In concert with a TUNEL assay it would be possible to determine if pitavastatin is inducing apoptosis or has some other secondary mechanism of action.

Time constraints prevented a 24 hour assay of both lovastatin and pitavastatin, however in summary our pitavastatin is currently the most effective inhibitor of *Acanthamoeba spp.* among the statins tested. This is the first record of pitavastatin being tested as an anti-acanthamoebic compound rendering this data novel. Atorvastatin was the second most effective inhibitor but lacks amoebicidal capability. Atorvastatin's activity fits with established literature, although the strains tested in this study appear to have a greater resistance to the compound (Martín-Navarro et al., 2013).

As noted type 1 statins did not show any effect against the *Acanthamoeba spp.* used. Lovastatin, has previously been shown to have little inhibitory effect on *Acanthamoeba spp.* and so its lack of inhibitory effect fits with the literature. Simvastatin was the only compound in contrast to established literature where it has been shown to have an IC_{50} of 10.24 μ M (Martín-Navarro et al., 2013). In addition, this is the first record of mevastatin being used as an anti-acanthamoeba compound and its results are entirely novel.

In the previous chapter, it was determined that there was no synergy between allylamines and 14- α -demethylase inhibitors. Our hypothesis was that a combination of enzyme upregulation and substrate competition was responsible for this lack of synergy. It was determined that selecting an indirectly related enzyme may allow for circumventing this feedback loop. Inhibition of HMGR and thus

mevalonate also affects several other biochemical pathways through IPP inhibition, providing additional stress to the cell once additional inhibitors were applied.

However, our data do not support this hypothesis, neither the allylamines nor azoles showed synergy with statins. Instead, our data suggest that statins induce have an antagonistic relationship with the other inhibitors, particularly with the allylamine, terbinafine.

The conclusion would be that statin treatment may be inducing cellular activity that is inhibiting the effects of downstream inhibitors. HMGR is tightly regulated in all species, as such inhibition of the enzyme may be actively inducing massive upregulation of HMGR and downstream enzymes (Toyota et al., 2020). This may be actively exacerbated with the addition of squalene epoxidase or 14- α -demethylase inhibition.

While these studies have shown no current synergistic potential, they have revealed new inhibitors that are effective against *Acanthamoeba spp.* likely through the inhibition of ergosterol synthesis. Subsequently, the *Acanthamoeba spp.* membranes would have been weakened through ergosterol inhibition.

The next step in these studies would, therefore, be to actively interfere with the membrane while simultaneously inhibiting the ability of *Acanthamoeba spp.* to increase ergosterol production. Chlorohexidine and Polyhexamethylene biguanide are the standard treatment against *Acanthamoeba spp.* and both their mechanism of action is through membrane disruption and will be used in concert with established inhibitors for synergy potential in the next study.

Overall, this study has proven that HMG-CoA reductase is a potent inhibitor in *Acanthamoeba spp.* with the potential to cause amoebicidal activity. The study shows that there is a clear difference in effectiveness between type 1 and type 2 statins as inhibitors. The research also shows that there is a potential antagonism between statins, azoles and allylamines. This study demonstrates that

atorvastatin and pitavastatin, show excellent inhibition against both isolates and thus may prove beneficial as part of a treatment course that does not include other sterol inhibitors.

**Chapter 5 Characterisation of the synergistic interaction of
biocides with sterol inhibitors *in-vivo***

5.1 The plasma membrane

The plasma membrane acts as a specific filter that separates the cell's contents from the external environment and provides a route of communication between internal and external environments. Composed primarily of phospholipids, amphipathic molecules consisting of a hydrophobic tail attached to a hydrophilic head, the membrane utilises a dual layer of these molecules to form itself(Singer and Nicolson, 1972).

The phospholipid heads align themselves together, facing towards either the outer environment or the inner cytoplasm. Simultaneously, the hydrophobic tails create a water-repellent inner layer; hence the term bilayer (Valitova, Sulkarnayeva and Minibayeva, 2016; Jordá and Puig, 2020).

Figure 5.1: Simplified diagram of the plasma membrane, showing the bilayer and associated proteins.

Created with BioRender.com

As a part of its function, the plasma membrane must be able to adjust both its rigidity and strength. Most frequently, this is achieved through the insertion of the lipids; cholesterol, ergosterol or stigmasterol depending on species (Hu *et al.*, 2017). Lipid insertion forces the bilayer into a tighter alignment, pushing the phospholipids closer together, thus increasing overall rigidity of the membrane. Lipids are also used in the creation of lipid rafts, areas of stability located on the membrane that are used as locations for receptors and cell signalling (Brown and London, 1998).

5.2 Cell membrane inhibition

Membrane dysregulation has been a key component of antimicrobial work since the advent of antibiotic research. For example, penicillin irreversibly binds to bacterial transpeptidase, responsible for completing the bacterial cell wall through cross-linking the peptide layers, inhibition of transpeptidase results in the bacterial membrane weakening and loss of osmotic regulation (Tipper and Strominger 1965; Yocum, Rasmussen, and Strominger 1980).

Azoles and squalene epoxidase (SQE), inhibitors tested in this thesis have similar mechanisms of action (Silva *et al.*, 2020; Thomson *et al.*, 2017). The primary benefit of these compounds as inhibitor targets for pathogens is that they interact with enzymes that are either not found in humans, such as penicillin; or inhibit enzymes that have structural differences from human versions, due to differing substrates, in the case of azoles and SQE inhibitors. These compounds preferentially bind to non-human versions of their target enzymes,

Disruption of lipid production via enzyme inhibition, has multiple consequences, the membrane will become significantly weaker due to the lack of lipid reinforcement. The limited levels of lipids will interfere with the production of lipid rafts, without which cell signalling and receptor presentation become more difficult. Finally, the membrane may rupture due to osmotic pressure; however, the cell may undergo apoptosis before this occurs.

Acanthamoeba keratitis (AK) treatment currently relies on a direct attack on the cell membrane through the use of detergents such as Chlorhexidine or PHMB(Lee et al., 2020). Unlike enzyme inhibitors, these compounds produce secondary effectors that interfere with the membrane through direct interaction.

While effective, these compounds are not specific for *Acanthamoeba spp.* and also interact human corneal cells. Furthermore, combined with the frequency of treatment required, AK patients currently find treatment incredibly arduous due to sleep disruption and severe pain. Decreasing the concentrations of these compounds necessary for proper efficacy, or enhancing the effectiveness through synergy would allow for a significant improvement in patient treatment.

5.3 Biocides in *Acanthamoeba* species

The first reported successful treatment of *Acanthamoeba* keratitis utilised a combination of propamidine and neomycin(Wright et al., 1985). Propamidine is a detergent frequently used in disinfectants, however its use in this study has since allowed for the incorporation of similar detergents in *Acanthamoeba* keratitis treatment.

As mentioned in the previous section biocides do not have a specific target, their mechanism of action instead works passively through electrostatic effect. Biocides structure contains a mixture of hydrophobic regions and a strong positive charge, rendering them cationic. This allows them to interact with the cells surface and integrate into the cytoplasmic reticulum (Figure5.2).

Membranes are a complex mix of peripheral and integral proteins with carefully regulated environments that control their function. Initial biocides interaction destroys this regulation through randomly displacing and disruption of the phospholipids and proteins resulting in severe disruption of the plasma membrane. Subsequent interactions rely on the individual biocide used, with pore formation or precipitation of the cytoplasm also possible (Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.2: Chemical structure of Chlorhexidine (A) and Polyhexamethylene biguanide (B). Cationic phospholipid-binding sites are highlighted in red, hydrophobic hexamethylene group in blue.

Figure 5.3 Diagrammatic representation of the interaction of chlorhexidine with the cytoplasmic membrane. The diagram shows the gradual decreases in the outer leaflet's fluidity with the increasing exposure to the bisbiguanide and the eventual cell leakage. Created with BioRender.com

In the treatment of *Acanthamoeba* keratitis, among most commonly used biocidal agents are chlorhexidine (CHX) and polyhexamethylene (PHMB) (Lee *et al.*, 2020)

(Alver *et al.* 2020; Joseph, Chaurasia, and Sharma 2018; Lee *et al.* 2020). The compounds belong to the bisbiguanide family of compounds and are the drugs of interest in this study.

5.4 Chlorhexidine and Polyhexamethylene in *Acanthamoeba* keratitis

Chlorhexidine and PHMB were among the earliest adopted treatments for *Acanthamoeba* keratitis and currently among the most common (Larkin *et al.*, 1992; Seal *et al.*, 1994). Both belong to the bisbiguanide family of compounds and have notably superior cysticidal capabilities than similar compounds (Khunkitti *et al.*, 1996).

Chlorhexidine was created in the early 1950s and has since become one of the most used biocidal agents in the world, found in soaps and mouthwash. 0.02% chlorhexidine eye drops saw use as a treatment in *Acanthamoeba* keratitis in 1994 and has since become a staple of *Acanthamoeba* keratitis treatment (Seal *et al.*, 1994). chlorhexidine primarily affects the membrane partitioning itself into the cell wall and damaging the membrane. High concentrations of chlorhexidine within the cell begin to cause coagulation of the cytoplasm, causing further damage (Hugo and Longworth, 1965).

Similar to chlorhexidine, PHMB is used as a disinfectant and antiseptic, used in *Acanthamoeba* keratitis treatment since 1992 it is generally treated as exchangeable with chlorhexidine. PHMB also directly interacts with the membrane but has additional actions in *Acanthamoeba* *spp.* with concentrations also causing apoptosis (Moon *et al.*, 2018).

5.5 Results

Using a previously standardised cell number (Table 5.1), the inhibitory capability of Chlorhexidine and Polyhexamethylene biguanide was assessed using a modified version of the alamarBlue™ microtiter plate assay as described by (McBride *et al.*, 2005).

CHX and PHM as individual inhibitors showed high amoebicidal capability at concentrations $\geq 5 \mu\text{M}$ and $\geq 15.6 \mu\text{M}$ respectively for both *A. castellanii* 50370 and *A. polyphaga* 50371. As expected, neither compound showed inhibitory effect below effective concentrations. CHX showed little synergistic activity with any of the compounds it was tested with, however PHM showed excellent synergy with both terbinafine and tioconazole and with particular concentrations of Voriconazole. However, neither biocide showed significant activity with the statins used. Cell death was shown in all cases where synergy was detected.

Synergy was determined using Combenifit™ analysis software according to the BLISS synergy predictive model.

Figure 5.4: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Lovastatin ($61.5 \mu\text{M} - 3.84 \mu\text{M}$) and Chlorhexidine ($10 \mu\text{M} - 0.625 \mu\text{M}$) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$

Figure 5.5: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Pitavastatin ($7.09 \mu\text{M}$ - $0.44 \mu\text{M}$) and Chlorhexidine ($10 \mu\text{M}$ - $0.625 \mu\text{M}$) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$ ***= $P < 0.0001$

Figure 5.6: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Terbinafine (32.16 μ M - 2.01 μ M) and CHX (10 μ M- 0.625 μ M) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$ ***= $P < 0.0001$

Figure 5.7: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Tioconazole (62.5 μ M – 3.91 μ M) and CHX (10 μ M – 0.625 μ M) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *=P<0.05
=P<0.001 *=P<0.0001

Figure 5.8: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Voriconazole ($4 \mu\text{M} - 0.25 \mu\text{M}$) and Chlorhexidine ($10 \mu\text{M} - 0.625 \mu\text{M}$) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$ ***= $P < 0.0001$

Figure 5.9: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of PHM (15.6 μ M – 0.975 μ M) and Chlorhexidine (10 μ M- 0.625 μ M) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$ ***= $P < 0.0001$

Figure 5.10: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Pitavastatin (7.09 μM - 0.44 μM) and PHM (15.6 μM - 0.975 μM) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed no synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$ ***= $P < 0.0001$

Figure 5.11: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Terbinafine (32.16 μM – 2.01 μM) and PHM (15.6 μM – 0.975 μM) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed strong synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$ ***= $P < 0.0001$

Figure 5.12: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Tioconazole ($62.5 \mu\text{M} - 3.91 \mu\text{M}$) and PHM ($15.6 \mu\text{M} - 0.975 \mu\text{M}$) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed strong synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$ ***= $P < 0.0001$

Figure 5.13: 2×10^3 trophozoites per well of the ATCC 50370 isolate of *A. castellanii* or the ATCC 50371 isolate of *A. polyphaga* were seeded in PG media with a combination of Voriconazole ($4 \mu\text{M} - 0.25 \mu\text{M}$) and PHM ($15.6 \mu\text{M} - 0.975 \mu\text{M}$) for 96 hours. Controls consisted of a positive without drug control, a media without drug control and a blank. The drug combinations showed strong synergy at the tested concentration combinations. Each value represents the mean of sextuplicate wells \pm SE, assay was carried out in sextuplicate. *= $P < 0.05$ **= $P < 0.001$ ***= $P < 0.0001$

5.6 Discussion

Current treatment regimens for *Acanthamoeba* rely on combination therapy of a biocide and another compound ranging from antifungals to antibacterials (REF). However, there has been no study into these drug combinations' synergistic effects, instead of relying on clinical success accounts. Therefore, this chapter aims to characterise two biocides' synergistic capabilities: chlorhexidine (CHX) and polyhexamethylene biguanide (PHMB) with sterol inhibitors against *Acanthamoeba spp.*

As expected from the literature, neither biocide had a typical dose-response curve, instead becoming completely amoebicidal at concentrations of 5 μM CHX and 15.6 μM PHMB. This, unfortunately, prevented the experiment from utilising concentrations similar to those found within eye-drops as it would have individually resulted in complete death of the test amoeba. Additionally, given eye drops are diluted quickly through tears, blinking, and surface area, it was considered unlikely that high concentrations are maintained.

Of most significant clinical interest is the differences in synergistic potential between CHX and PHMB. As noted, both compounds are commonly used against *Acanthamoeba spp.* with the biocides being treated almost interchangeably. This study shows that this attitude is in error, CHX shows almost no synergistic interaction with any other compounds. At the same time, PHMB significantly enhances the amoebicidal capabilities of tioconazole and terbinafine compounds that otherwise are only amoebastatic.

The synergistic potential of pitavastatin and voriconazole is of note, both compounds are alone in their amoebicidal capabilities compared to their respective families. Despite this, neither compound shows the more generalised enhancement of tioconazole and terbinafine, instead only showing a narrow band in which their capabilities are enhanced. This may agree with our previous hypothesis that these compounds have a secondary mechanism of action responsible for cell killing, which is not improved with the biocide.

The reason behind these differences are unknown, and identifying exact biocide activity is difficult due to their wide range of effects. However, whatever interaction CHX is having with the membrane may be so weak that the membrane adapts even when weakened through sterol inhibitors. This would be compared to PHMB, which significantly enhances the capabilities of tioconazole and terbinafine (Figures 5.11 and 5.12).

This study confirms our hypothesis that a combination of sterol inhibitor and biocides have synergistic interaction. However, the data also shows that clinically CHX may be less overall effective than PHMB as CHX does not show synergistic potential with any of the compounds used.

Chapter 6 **GC-MS optimisation for *Acanthamoeba spp.***

6.1 Background

Sterol synthesis is a basic metabolic pathway of eukaryotes giving rise to essential membrane components. While these pathways can be generalised, species pathways are unique and can have unexpected methods of producing end-sterol products. Understanding these pathways and how inhibitors interact with them is essential in ensuring that the drugs have the expected activity or additional mechanisms.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) is an analytical method composed of two primary components. Gas chromatography separates molecules depending on their relative chemical affinity to a stationary column, depending on a combination of the columns dimensions (length, diameter, film thickness) and the phase properties. This results in the grouping of molecules with similar chemical affinity which then elute from the column at different times. The molecules are fed into the Mass-Spectrometer which breaks the molecules into ionized fragments and proceeds to detect them based on their mass-to-charge ratio. When compared to controls this allows for the identification of a particular molecule even within a sample containing a complex mix of compounds.

Previously, we showed that 7-dehydrostigmasterol was not detected in *Acanthamoeba* (Thomson, Christopher A Rice, *et al.*, 2017) compared to data published by Smith and Korn (Smith and Korn, 1968). This was later rebutted by Zhou *et al.* (Zhou *et al.*, 2018) which showed a clear peak for 7-dehydrostigmasterol. These studies' conflicting data may be attributed to differences in methodology during extraction or chromatography processes.

As such, comparing and enhancing the previous methods would optimise the methodology and prevent further conflicts. Additionally, these methods would allow for further investigation into the mode of action of statins, SQE inhibitors and azoles, allowing for confirmation of the theoretical sterol synthesis pathway of *Acanthamoeba spp.*

6.2 Aims

This chapter aims to compare various GC-MS protocols to optimise both the methods for extraction and chromatography. To achieve this, sterol extracts of *Acanthamoeba* will be run through three different extraction methods; Derivatisation, solid-phase extraction and evaporation. These extracts will then be run through three differing GC-MS methods; one taken from (Thomson, Christopher A Rice, *et al.*, 2017), the rebuttal method from (Zhou *et al.*, 2018); and finally data taken from these two methods will then be utilised to create an optimised methodology for *Acanthamoeba* spp. This study then utilised this optimal method to assess sterol inhibitors' effects to further elucidate their mechanism of action.

6.3 Results

Sterol extracts from *Acanthamoeba polyphaga* were run through three different preparation methods. Both Ergosterol and 7-dehydrostigmasterol were confirmed to be found in the sterol extract in all methods used.

The first methods involved utilising a sterol extraction kit (2.10.1.2) (Sigma, UK) to rapidly resolve the sterols while also providing an internal standard in the form of cholestane. While sampling with the kit was significantly simpler, the internal standard masked squalene from being detected on the GC-MS.

Despite multiple attempts to overcome the masking effect eventually a standard overnight evaporation technique was used, with the sterol extract allowed to air evaporate overnight (2.10.2.3). Attempts to increase resolution using derivatization (2.10.2.1) and solid phase extraction techniques (2.10.2.2) were also attempted.

However, derivatisation with BSTFA failed, greatly depressing peaks and resulting in poor returns. Solid phase extraction removed all excess peaks bar the ergosterol and 7-dehydrostigmasterol but introduced contamination and reduced resolution of the peaks. As both techniques may have masked changes of interest in the sterol profile it was decided that the standard evaporation technique would be utilised going forward with the technique providing the best overall resolution (Figure 6.2).

The third method was solid phase extraction. It was found to remove nearly all excess peaks bar the two end products of ergosterol and 7-dehydrostigmasterol but introduced contamination and reduced resolution of the peaks. Derivatisation with BSTFA failed and instead greatly depressed the peaks resulting in poor returns.

After optimisation of the extraction protocol the optimisation of the GC-MS runtime was carried out. Initially protocol Sterols 1 (2.10.3.1) based on a protocol from a previous study was used (Thomson, Christopher A Rice, *et al.*, 2017). However the protocol was poorly optimised for sterol separation,

requiring both a significant period of time per sample and providing poor separation (Figure 6.1). Protocol Sterols 2 (2.10.3.2) was then created based on a more recent study examining *Acanthamoeba* spp. sterols (Zhou *et al.*, 2018). While requiring significantly less time than Sterols 1 the timeframes were far too short for proper readings. The high starting temperature of the oven combined with the rapid heating to decrease sample analysis time lead to poor peak resolution (Figure 6.1).

Protocol Sterols 3 (2.10.3.3) was based on a combination of the other two protocols and was found to give the best overall chromatography and mass spec data within an acceptable timeframe (Figure 6.1).

Once the GC-MS was optimised sterol extracts of *Acanthamoeba* spp. treated with sub-lethal doses of terbinafine were analysed through the GC-MS. Terbinafine was confirmed through GC-MS to effect *Acanthamoeba* spp. through squalene epoxidase inhibition. Controls clearly show no detectable squalene peak until terbinafine is added at which point squalene clearly becomes detectable (Figures 6.5 and 6.6). Samples similarly treated with voriconazole were also ran through as a test of the optimisation. The new resolution allowed for a far clearer picture of voriconazole inhibiting lanosterol-14-alpha demethylase through both peak downturn and the observation of obstiofoliol (Figures 6.5 and 6.6).

6.3.1 GC-MS protocol comparison shows Sterols 3 protocol gave the best chromatography

Figure 6.1: Figure shows the chromatograms of GC-MS protocols Sterol 1 (A) Sterols 2 (B) and Sterols 3 (C), Chromatogram shows best peak resolution and separation with Sterols 3.

6.3.2 Atmospheric evaporation followed by reconstitution in chloroform was the most effective method of sample preparation

Figure 6.2: Figure shows the chromatograms of GC-MS protocols Sterol 2 (A,C,E) and Sterol 3 (B,D,F) with derivatised sterol extract. Chromatograms A and B are controls, C and D have been treated with Terbinafine and E and F treated with Voriconazole.

Figure 6.3: Figure shows the chromatograms of GC-MS protocols Sterol 2 (A,C,E) and Sterols 3 (B,D,F) with sterol extract through solid phase extraction. Chromatograms A and B are controls, C and D have been treated with Terbinafine and E and F treated with Voriconazole.

Figure 6.4 Figure shows the chromatograms of GC-MS protocols Sterol 2 (A,C,E) and Sterols 3 (B,D,F) with sterol extract through evaporation. Chromatograms A and B are controls, D has been treated with Terbinafine and E and F treated with Voriconazole. Data not shown for Sterols 2 terbinafine.

6.3.3 Terbinafine acts through SQE inhibition and Voriconazole inhibition causes accumulation of obtusifoliol

Figure 6.5: Figure shows the chromatograms of a 48hr *Acanthamoeba castellanii* sterol extract using evaporation extraction and Sterols 3 protocol. A is the control extract, B is treated with terbinafine and C is treated with voriconazole. Red square shows squalene peak produced through terbinafine inhibition; black square shows the obstifoliol peak produced through voriconazole inhibition.

Figure 6.6 Figure shows the chromatograms of a 72 hr *Acanthamoeba castellanii* sterol extract using evaporation extraction and Sterols 3 protocol. A is the control extract, B is treated with terbinafine and C is treated with voriconazole. Red square shows squalene peak produced through terbinafine inhibition; black square shows the obstifolol peak produced through voriconazole inhibition.

6.3.4 Column polarity is essential for the separation of cycloartenol and lanosterol

Figure 6.7 Figure shows the chromatograms of lanosterol standard and a cycloartenol standard using Sterols 3. Peak A is Lanost-8-en-3 β -ol B is Lanosterol and C is Cycloartenol

6.4 Discussion

This chapter standardised and optimised extraction methods and a GC-MS protocol specific for *Acanthamoeba* sterol investigation. Our initial experiments were based on a previous study completed by this lab group. However, we found the method was less than optimal as the column used was non-polar and not optimised for the sterol study. Changing the column from a 5% to a 50% polar column allowed for a greater degree of separation, however, we still found the protocol took a significant period between samples.

Following identification of 7-dehydrostigmasterol in *Acanthamoeba* (Zhou *et al.*, 2018), the reasons for not having detected the sterol in Thomson *et al.*, (2017) were explored. An identical protocol and attempt to achieve proper separation based on the new protocol. Issues were encountered with the short runtime of the protocol combined with the rapid heating caused the sample to run through the GC-MS that the only peaks that could be detected at any point were ergosterol and 7-dehydrostigmasterol, which did not allow for proper analysis of our drugs mechanism of action.

After exploring these two methods a third was created based on a combination of the two above, by lowering the oven temp and heating slower compared to Zhou *et al.*, (2018); while utilising the 50% column and increasing overall runtime similar to our initial method we found significantly increased resolution while also having an acceptable runtime.

Once this protocol was established sterol extracts from *Acanthamoeba castellanii* treated with the IC50 of selected drugs were run through the GC-MS. Initially we were unable to detect squalene, this was discovered to be due to the internal standard used in the extraction kit we had been utilising. Once modified to account for these issues the build-up of squalene was easily identified (Figure 6.4) and confirmed that Terbinafines activity on *Acanthamoeba* via the SQE.

The voriconazole results raised a challenge we had not been expecting and were unable to fully resolve. After treatment with voriconazole, a small off-peak was shown in the Ergosterol peak, this

offshoot is most likely obstifoliol but there is a small probability that it may be lanosterol as the two are isomers. Multiple attempts were made to further separate these peaks for proper identification, a protocol was eventually created. Sterols 3 was shown to be capable of separating cycloartenol and lanosterol in a mix suggesting it may allow for separation of the lanosterol/obstifoliol/ergosterol peak but time did not permit the experiment that would have identified the peak.

In addition to this protocol, other options were explored but time or equipment did not permit. A chiral column would have allowed for proper separation however it would require a rework of the protocol as the temperature is currently too high for the column. An MS-MS would give complete resolution to the issue, but the equipment was not available at the time.

Overall, this chapter has optimised a methodology for sterol extraction and running of an *Acanthamoeba* sterol extract. Further the study has confirmed that ergosterol and 7-dehydrostigmasterol are primary components of *Acanthamoeba spp.* plasma membrane. The study has also confirmed the mechanism of action of terbinafine and voriconazole.

Chapter 7 Integration of a GFP-expressing plasmid into

Acanthamoeba spp.

7.1 Background

One of the primary toolkits in the development of treatment for any pathogen is genetic modification. The ability to turn genes on or off as needed allows for a vast increase in knowledge of essential genetic pathways and with this knowledge new drug targets. There has been very little genetic work compiled on *Acanthamoeba* spp. particularly regarding to genetic modification. There are currently no modified cell lines available nor any fluorescent cell lines. The creation of such a line would be a significant advancement for the understanding of *Acanthamoeba*.

In particular a GFP expressing *Acanthamoeba* would offer an alternative and, if necessary, a correlating factor in drug effectiveness. Once suitably optimized a fluorescence-based assay would also allow for drug effectiveness to be measured over a period rather than at a single time-point. Furthermore, once the technique is proven it would be possible to modify the plasmid to allow for more in-depth studies by allowing for protein and gene investigations.

Perhaps the closest recently was a study using Cas9 to create a mutant strain through gene deletion(Huang *et al.*, 2019). However, while this paper successfully created a mutant cell line the technique is prolonged and would not allow for further modification. This would involve the complete integration of a CRISPR/Cas9 system onto a plasmid then carried into the *Acanthamoeba*. This would therefore allow for the rapid modification of the cell line.

Previously an attempt to create a GFP-expressing *Acanthamoeba* was developed by Dr Wiese of Strathclyde University. However, there were multiple issues, *Acanthamoeba* spp. do not retain plasmids for more than a few generations unless continual drug pressure is maintained, and there were difficulties with the promoter.

7.2 Aims

The aim of this chapter is to create a GFP-expressing *Acanthamoeba* Neff strain with the express goal of utilising the modified species in drug assays and compared to the Alamarblue™ Assay. This would be achieved through the creation of a fluorescent assay with an untreated positive sample treated as the control fluorescence. Similar to the current Alamarblue™ assay but no longer requiring any additional compounds. Furthermore, the optimisation of the transfection methodology may then be utilised further to create a *Acanthamoeba* spp. cell line that can be quickly and permanently modified through the use of CRISPR/Cas9.

7.3 Results

7.3.1 Restriction Digest of pBAExpress

pBAExpress was successfully digested as described (2.12.1) and was confirmed by gel electrophoresis showing fragments at 1540 bp and 5578 bp. The 5578 bp fragment was extracted (2.12.3) and underwent SAP treatment to prevent the fragment from spontaneous religation.

Figure 7.1: Plasmid map of pBAExpress

Figure 7.2: L. 10 kbp ladder R1. The restriction digest of pBAExpress with BgIII and NheI showing two fragments of the expected sizes of 5578 and 1540 bp.

7.3.2 Restriction Digest of pBBSDRFPCSV40

The SV40 promoter was successfully removed through restriction digest as described (2.12.2) and the digest confirmed through gel electrophoresis. The 424 bp fragment was extracted (2.12.3).

Figure 7.3: Plasmid map of pBBSDRFPCSV40.

Figure 7.4 L. 10 kbp ladder R1. Restriction digest of pBBSDRFPCSV40 with BgIII and XbaI. Digest shows the expected fragment sizes of 424 and 4825

7.3.3 Confirmation of Successful Development of pBASV40GFP

The pBAExpress and pBBSDRFPCSV40 fragments were ligated (2.12.5) to create pBASV40GFP.

Confirmation of a successful ligation was carried out utilising a test digest (2.12.8) and confirmed

through gel electrophoresis. pBASV40GFP was then transformed into *Acanthamoeba* NEFF (2.12.11)

creating a GFP expressing *Acanthamoeba* (Figure 7.8).

Figure 7.5: Plasmid map of pBASV40.

Figure 7.6: L. 10 kbp ladder R. 1-6 Restriction digest of the six ligation reactions with NcoI. R. 1,3 and 5 show the expected fragment patterns for the digest generating fragments of 3995 and 2007.

Figure 7.7: Figure shows the test restriction digest of pBASV40GFP. L. 10 kbp Ladder R1. AvrII digest showing expected fragments of 3288 and 2714 bp R2. BglII digest showing an expected band of 6002 bp R3. NcoI digest showing expected fragments at 3288 and 2714 bp

Figure 7.8: Figure shows the pictures taken of Neff control cells without the pBASV40GFP plasmid (top) and the pBASV40GFP containing *Acanthamoeba* (bottom). The picture shows that the control cells show some autofluorescence. The pBASV40GFP containing *Acanthamoeba* shows significantly greater fluorescence across the entire cell.

7.3.4 Confirmation of GFP-expression through Western blot

While microscopic analysis showed that there was GFP-expression in the modified *Acanthamoeba*. However, there was still some concern over expression levels a Western blot was conducted to ensure expression.

Figure 7.9: Complete protein lysate of Neff sample pellets (2×10^6 , 1×10^6 and 5×10^5) and positive control pellets from GFP expressing *E. coli* (5, 10, 15 and 20 μ l of media). GFP band shows at 27kDa (Highlighted).

Figure 7.10: Figure shows the Western blot of the complete protein lysate of Neff sample pellets (2×10^6 , 1×10^6 and 5×10^5) and positive control pellets from GFP expressing *E. coli* (5, 10, 15 and 20µl of media). GFP band shows at 27kDa (Highlighted).

7.4 Generation of a RFP-Expressing *Acanthamoeba*

Despite successfully creating a GFP-expressing *Acanthamoeba* an issue was found with autofluorescence interfering with the results. A previous attempt to create a temporary GFP expressing *Acanthamoeba* spp. cell line has been attempted, however as no negative control was used autofluorescence was not checked for (Kong and Pollard, 2002). As such it was decided to create an RFP-expressing *Acanthamoeba*. Given time constraints much of the work was done in conjunction with my colleague Mr Sanchez. The sequence alignment of the plasmid pRFPSV40 showed successful sequence alignment.

Figure 7.11: The figure shows the sequencing alignment of pRFPSV40. Comma shows consensus letter shows unmatched, Figure shows the construct matches the reference and the successful creation of the plasmid.

7.5 Discussion

A GFP-expressing *Acanthamoeba* was successfully created, however there were significant difficulties with the process. The amoeba quickly lost the plasmid whenever not placed under continual drug pressure and so could not be utilised in other drug assays due to potential drug interference.

Additionally, it was found the amoeba were resistant to G418 the negative control utilised throughout the experiment meaning that even cells with a low copy number of the plasmid were surviving relatively intact. This meant that overall fluorescence was low among the modified amoeba. Which was made abundant whenever the amoeba were compared to a control under the fluorescent microscope as it was found *Acanthamoeba* have natural autofluorescence. Attempts were made to fix this through increasing the G418 concentration however this lowered overall growth and rendered experiments difficult without much increase in GFP potency.

With these restrictions in place, it was decided that a more optimal solution would be to create a RFP-expressing plasmid that would be less affected by the autofluorescence. Utilising the initial GFP plasmid a colleague proceeded to assist in the creation of such a plasmid. However, time did not permit for the transfection of the amoeba.

From here the successful creation of the RFP-plasmid will allow for rapid tracking of modified amoeba. However, the resistance *Acanthamoeba* showed to G418 even without modification suggests that there may need to be an exploration of other control drugs in order to ensure the cell death of unmodified amoeba.

Should these two objectives be met the last experiment to attempt would be to place a full CRISPR/Cas9 system within the amoeba to create a cell line that can be rapidly modified. This would be a significant boon to the understanding of this not well understood organism.

Chapter 8 Conclusion

Acanthamoeba species are the causative agents of *Acanthamoeba* keratitis, Granulomatous amoebic encephalitis and cutaneous acanthamoebiasis. The present drug regime is arduous on the patient and ineffectual should the amoeba successfully encyst. While new drug regimens that are effective against cysts would be optimal there is still a severe dearth in our understanding of standard treatments. This included the actual synergistic potential of the commonly used biocides Chlorhexidine and polyhexamethylene biguanide (Marciano-Cabral and Cabral, 2003; Visvesvara, Moura and Schuster, 2007). This thesis has aimed to acknowledge and elucidate on some of these questions.

In this thesis the sterol biosynthesis of *Acanthamoeba spp.* was investigated in order to further expand on the pathways capability as a drug target. Squalene epoxidase inhibitors were characterised as a promising new treatment option against *Acanthamoeba spp.* Novel statins have been used and potentially found to have a pattern of effect. Investigation into biocides resulted in some interesting clinical applications and the optimisation of a GC-MS protocol allowed for the rapid confirmation of the sterol inhibitors mechanism of action, as well as opening some new questions into the sterol biosynthesis pathway of *Acanthamoeba spp.*

8.1 Squalene epoxidase

Found on the endoplasmic reticulum, squalene epoxidase catalyses the first step in sterol biosynthesis. A common target in antifungal treatment, the potential for crossover effect similar to that of the azoles (Thomson, Christopher A Rice, *et al.*, 2017) led to the inclusion of these compounds as a potential treatment for *Acanthamoeba*.

Currently there is no published data available on squalene epoxidase inhibitors as this enzyme has not been targeted in treatment. However, my data consistently shows effective inhibitory effects with terbinafine the most potent. Additionally terbinafine showed great synergy with the biocide polyhexamethylene biguanide the combination of which was amoebicidal. Squalene epoxidase

shows excellent potential as a treatment option, however further exploration of the family may be required to find their true capabilities.

However the study was not without its weaknesses, time limited the scope of the study to only a few of the available inhibitors. This may have lead to the weakest part of the study, none of the inhibitors testing showed amoebicidal capability as a monotherapy, a property that was found during testing with the other two studies. Additionally there is very limited information available on the activity of SE inhibitors leaving questions on their targeting and inhibitory mechanisms. This may tie into the data found with the GC-MS, while Squalene was shown to be inhibited there is little evidence that the amoeba is being deprived of an essential building block suggesting that there may be corrective mechanisms ensuring squalene production. A potential topic to study in the future.

Clinically these results are an important keystone in the confirmation that antifungal agents are excellent treatment options against *Acanthamoeba* spp. in the absence of funding for specifically defined treatments. While not among the most potent found in this thesis as a monotherapy the compounds have the advantage of broad synergy with PHMB significantly increasing their potency. The inhibitors have the additional advantages of being well studied and well tolerated by humans allowing for rapid adaption into the clinic in the event of *Acanthamoeba* spp. resistance to more common treatments.

8.2 Statins

Responsible for the production of mevalonate and the rate-limiting step, HMGR is the target of statins. Due to their significantly different target in the sterol synthesis pathway when compared to azoles and SQE inhibitors I hypothesised that they may potentially have synergistic capability that SQE inhibitors failed to show.

This hypothesis was boosted by previous research that showed statins successfully utilised in *Acanthamoeba* spp. treatment (Silva *et al.*, 2020). My studies add significantly to this research

through utilising the statins in more clinical settings through utilising them as a combination therapy. However despite broad attempts at finding synergistic interaction there was none detected with either of the other inhibitor families. Pitavastatin was however found to be a highly effective compound with amoebicidal capabilities the data of which is completely novel in relation to *Acanthamoeba* spp.

Similar to the SQE inhibitors a weakness of this study is in how broad it is. While vastly increasing our knowledge of the effects of statins on *Acanthamoeba* spp. several of the statins were not properly utilised due to a combination of inexperience and time not allowing for correction. Similar to voriconazole pitavastatin is amoebicidal as a monotherapy; however, the reasons behind this effect remain unknown as none of the other compounds show similar capabilities. An incredibly useful future study would be to try and identify the secondary mechanisms of effect that allow for these compounds to be amoebicidal at relatively low concentrations.

Similar to the SQE results this study shows the potential of utilising well established compounds utilised against related organisms to treat understudied pathogens. While proper testing of the type 1 statins will have to occur for proper evaluation the beginning results are promising. Particularly the effects of pitavastatin which showed excellent potential as a monotherapy, however the lack of interaction with either 14- α -demethylase inhibitors or SQE inhibitors does present questions. The complete lack of interaction between enzyme inhibitors is fascinating and attempting to identify if this is simply due to transportation limitations or some form of protection would be a potent study in the quest for a treatment against *Acanthamoeba* spp.

8.3 Biocides

Among the most common and first response treatment to *Acanthamoeba* keratitis infection CHX and PHMB have been utilised since the early 1990s. Despite this however there was no published data on their synergistic potential which this thesis aimed to elucidate.

The question of biocide interaction came late in the study shortly after testing with statins. Their common use in *Acanthamoeba* spp. treatment presupposed me to the belief that synergy testing had occurred at some point in the past. It was only after multiple attempts at synergistically inhibiting the sterol biosynthesis pathway that I looked into inhibiting the pathway while simultaneously weakening the membrane. This interest led to the discovery that there was no information available on the interaction of biocides with any of the compounds utilised in treatment. This is despite biocide treatment being the first response treatment to *Acanthamoeba* keratitis infection with CHX and PHMB utilised since the early 1990s.

My study showed that unlike previously thought CHX has little to no interaction with any of the inhibitors tested. This is of extreme clinical relevance as CHX is a front-line treatment against *Acanthamoeba* keratitis and the use of this compound is decreasing the success of patient treatment outcome. PHMB however has been found to have broad synergistic capabilities with enzyme inhibitors.

A weakness in the study is that PHMB or CHX was not utilised in combination with propamidine or neomycin leaving gaps within the pattern of data. This could be rapidly checked with the AlamarBlue assay and would leave little question of whether PHMB should be utilised as the first treatment option in combination therapy due to its broad synergistic capabilities rendering it a safer and more effective treatment option than CHX.

8.4 GC-MS Optimisation

GC-MS is a powerful analytical technique that clarifies and proves the underlying mechanisms of action for sterol inhibitors. However, proper optimisation of the methodology and device is essential for robust results. Previously I showed that voriconazoles mechanism of action is based on the inhibition of 14- α -demethylase even if the secondary effects that underly its amoebicidal capability remain unknown.

However, the poor optimisation of the GC-MS methodology and device prevented a full analysis of the sterol products and may have also hidden additional sterols of interest. Optimisation of the technique therefore was of key concern in the study, particularly since it would allow for further exploration of the mechanisms of action of the other sterol inhibitors.

Optimisation of the GC-MS was complex but achieved towards the end of the study rendering the study of sterol metabolism relatively simple. This allowed for the confirmation of the mechanism of action of terbinafine and as a follow up to the previous study a confirmation of the effects of voriconazole.

The study of voriconazole raised some interesting problems that could have been solved given more time. It was found that both lanosterol and obtifoliol are chiral, this rendered identification complex however the use of either a chiral column or a GC-MS-MS would allow for identification and confirmation of the product. Identification of this product would massively expand on our understanding of the complex sterol biosynthesis pathway that *Acanthamoeba* spp. utilise.

8.5 Integration of a GFP-expressing plasmid into *Acanthamoeba* spp.

Examination of the physical characteristics of a parasite allows for advancement towards a treatment. However the information that can be found through interrogation of the genome can vastly increase this advancement. Currently modification of the *Acanthamoeba* spp. genome is not a simple process and there are no genetically modified strains easily available.

To create a CRISPR/Cas 9 strain of *Acanthamoeba* spp. I attempted to initially create a GFP expressing amoeba through the addition of a plasmid. With the kind assistance of Dr Martin Weise from Strathclyde the plasmid pBAExpress was modified into pBASV40 by replacing a faulty promoter. Transformation of *Acanthamoeba* spp. was confirmed through western blott and later through microscopy. While successfully showing the integration of the plasmid and the compatibility

of the promoters further analysis showed autofluorescence of the amoeba at the same wavelength of the GFP.

Modification of the pBASV40 was then carried out through the removal and replacement of the GFP gene with an RFP reporter gene. Success of the modification was confirmed via sequence alignment, which showed the plasmid was ready to be used.

Continuing with this study is essential to the creation of an permanently modifiable cell line of *Acanthamoeba* spp. The possibilities of this research are incredibly potent, including the creation of cheaper more accurate assays, the modification of *Acanthamoeba* spp. genome for research purposes and further understanding the requirements for the genetic modification of understudied organisms.

8.6 Summary

In conclusion squalene epoxidase and HMGR demonstrate excellent potential as drug targets against *Acanthamoeba* spp. as an addition to current treatment.

Tested individually the SQE inhibitors only showed amoebistatic potential, however when utilised in combination with PHMB amoebicidal capabilities were observed. However no synergistic effect was observed with any of the other compounds tested. GC-MS analysis confirmed that the compounds effect was through squalene inhibition.

The group 1 statins showed no effect against *Acanthamoeba* spp. however this could be due to improper activation. The group 2 statins all showed good effect against *Acanthamoeba* spp. with pitavastatin showing amoebicidal capabilities individually. Pitavastatin however showed less synergistic interaction with PHMB than the SQE inhibitors.

The most significant finding of this thesis shows in the biocide synergy study. The difference in synergistic potential between PHMB and CHX was unexpected and of extreme clinical significance. In contrast to expectations based on the literature CHX showed no synergistic capability with any of

the compounds tested while PHMB showed synergy with other compounds. This essentially means that treatment of *Acanthamoeba* keratitis with CHX and any of the sterol inhibitors is of utterly no benefit to monotherapy of either compound. The harm this could be causing patients at this moment in time cannot be understated.

A GC-MS protocol optimised for *Acanthamoeba* sterol work was created and explored, confirming the mechanism of action of terbinafine and voriconazole and opening a path to further expand on.

A GFP-expressing *Acanthamoeba* cell-line was created however continual drug pressure was required to maintain the plasmid and autofluorescence required the plasmid be reworked to express RFP. However the created plasmid is capable of acting as the backbone for a CRISPR/Cas 9 expressing cell line of *Acanthamoeba* spp.

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